

Math 142A: Real Analysis I

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by Kenneth A. Ross

Course Notes and Solutions

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Math 142A Definitions and Theorems Sheet

Definitions

- **Definition 2.1 (Absolute value).** For $x \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$|x| := \begin{cases} x, & x \geq 0, \\ -x, & x < 0. \end{cases}$$

We say $|x|$ is the absolute value of x .

- **Definition 2.2 (Distance).** For $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$, the distance between a and b is defined by $\text{dist}(a, b) := |a - b|$.
- **Definition 3.1 (Bounds, max, min).** Let $S \subset \mathbb{R}$ be a nonempty subset.
A number $M \in \mathbb{R}$ is an upper bound of S if $s \leq M$ for all $s \in S$; $m \in \mathbb{R}$ is a lower bound of S if $m \leq s$ for all $s \in S$; The set S is said to be bounded if S have both an upper bound and a lower bound.
If $M \in S$ and M is an upper bound of S , we call M the maximum of S and write $M = \max S$. If $m \in S$ and m is a lower bound of S , we call m the minimum of S and write $m = \min S$.
- **Completeness Axiom.** Every nonempty subset $S \subset \mathbb{R}$ that is bounded from above has a supremum in \mathbb{R} .
- **Definition 3.3 (Least upper bound and greatest lower bound).** If $S \subset \mathbb{R}$ is nonempty and bounded from above, its supremum (least upper bound) is

$$\begin{aligned} \sup S &:= \text{the minimum of all upper bounds of } S \\ &= \min\{A \in \mathbb{R} \mid s \leq A \text{ for all } s \in S\}. \end{aligned}$$

If $S \subset \mathbb{R}$ is nonempty and bounded from below, its infimum (greatest lower bound) is defined as

$$\inf S := \max\{a \in \mathbb{R} \mid a \leq s \text{ for all } s \in S\}.$$

- **Definition 5.1 (Sequence).** A sequence is a function whose domain is set A of the form $A = \{n \in \mathbb{Z} \mid n \geq m\}$ for some $m \in \mathbb{Z}$. Usually we take $m = 0$ or $m = 1$.
Given a sequence $s : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, we usually write s_n instead of $s(n)$ and denote the sequence by

$$\{s_n\}_{n=m}^{\infty} = \{s_1, s_2, \dots\}.$$

When there is no ambiguity, people also shorten the notation $\{s_n\}_{n=m}^{\infty}$ by $\{s_n\}$.

- **Definition 5.3 (Limit of a sequence).** A sequence $\{s_n\}_{n=m}^{\infty}$ of real numbers converges to $s \in \mathbb{R}$ if for every $\epsilon > 0$ there is an $N \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$|s_n - s| < \epsilon \quad \text{for all } n > N.$$

We say that s is the limit of the sequence and write $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} s_n = s$ or $s_n \rightarrow s$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. When there is no ambiguity, we shorten the notations by $\lim s_n = s$ or $s_n \rightarrow s$.

A sequence that does not converge to any real number is said to diverge.

- **Definition 8.1.** Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence. We write $\lim s_n = +\infty$ if for each $M > 0$ there is a number N such that

$$s_n > M \quad \text{for all } n > N.$$

In this case, we say that the sequence $\{s_n\}$ diverges to ∞ . Similarly, we write $\lim s_n = -\infty$ if for each $M > 0$ there is a number N such that

$$s_n < -M \quad \text{for all } n > N.$$

In this case, we say that the sequence $\{s_n\}$ diverges to $-\infty$.
With the above definition, we will say $\{s_n\}$ has a limit or the limit exists if $\{s_n\}$ converges or diverges to $+\infty(-\infty)$. Sometimes, equivalent to say $\{s_n\}$ converges, we say the limit of $\{s_n\}$ exists and finite.

- **Definition 9.1.** Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence of real numbers. We say $\{s_n\}$ is an increasing sequence if $s_n \leq s_{n+1}$ for all n . We say $\{s_n\}$ is a decreasing sequence if $s_n \geq s_{n+1}$ for all n .

We say $\{s_n\}$ is a monotone sequence if it is either an increasing sequence or a decreasing sequence.

- **Definition 9.7.** Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence of real numbers. We define

$$\limsup s_n := \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sup\{s_n \mid n > N\},$$

$$\liminf s_n := \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \inf\{s_n \mid n > N\}.$$

- **Definition 10.1.** A sequence $\{s_n\}$ of real numbers is called a Cauchy sequence if for each $\epsilon > 0$, there exists a number N such that $|s_n - s_m| < \epsilon$ for all $m, n \geq N$.

In words, the definition of a Cauchy sequence is saying that the distance between any two terms, say s_n and s_m , of a Cauchy sequence can be as closed as you wish when their indices n and m are sufficiently large.

- **Definition 12.1.** Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence. A subsequence of this sequence is a sequence of the form $\{t_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ where for each k there is a positive number n_k such that

$$n_1 < n_2 < \dots < n_k < n_{k+1} < \dots \quad \text{and } t_k = s_{n_k}.$$

We usually phrase that $\{s_{n_k}\}_k$ (or shorter, $\{s_{n_k}\}$) is a subsequence of $\{s_n\}$.

- **Definition 15.1.** We say that the series $\sum_{k=m}^{\infty} a_k$ converges if the sequence $\{s_n\}_{k=m}^{\infty}$ of its partial sums converges to a real number s , i.e. $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=m}^n a_k = s$, in which case we write $\sum_{k=m}^{\infty} a_k = s$.

A series that does not converge is said to diverge. We say that the series $\sum_{k=m}^{\infty} a_k$ diverges to $+\infty$ if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} s_n = +\infty$. In this case, we write $\sum_{k=m}^{\infty} a_k = +\infty$. Likewise, we say that the series $\sum_{k=m}^{\infty} a_k$ diverges to $-\infty$ if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} s_n = -\infty$. In this case, we write $\sum_{k=m}^{\infty} a_k = -\infty$.

- **Definition 15.3.** A series $\sum a_k$ satisfies the Cauchy criterion if its partial sums $\{s_n\}$ form a Cauchy sequence, i.e. for each $\epsilon > 0$, there exists an N such that

$$|s_n - s_m| < \epsilon \quad \text{for all } n, m > N.$$

Equivalently, a series $\sum a_k$ satisfies the Cauchy criterion if for every $\epsilon > 0$, there exists an N such that

$$\left| \sum_{k=m}^n a_k \right| < \epsilon \quad \text{for all } n \geq m > N.$$

- **Definition 16.1.** We say that a series $\sum a_n$ converges absolutely (or is absolutely convergent) if $\sum |a_k|$ converges.

- **Definition 20.1.** Let f be a real-valued function defined on $S \subset \mathbb{R}$. We say f is continuous at $x_0 \in S$ if for every sequence $\{x_n\} \subset S$ converging to x_0 , we have $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n) = f(x_0)$.

If f is continuous at every point in S , then we say f is continuous in S , denoted by $f \in C^0(S)$ or $f \in C(S)$.

- **Definition 24.1.** Let f be a real valued function defined on $S \subset \mathbb{R}$. We say f is continuous at $x_0 \in S$ if

$$\forall \epsilon > 0, \exists \delta > 0 \text{ such that } |f(x) - f(x_0)| < \epsilon \\ \text{for all } x \in S \text{ with } |x - x_0| < \delta.$$

- **Definition 24.2 (Uniform continuity).** Let f be a real-valued function on $S \subset \mathbb{R}$. We say that f is uniformly continuous on a set S if for any $\epsilon > 0$, there exists $\delta > 0$ s.t. $|f(x) - f(y)| < \epsilon$ for all $x, y \in S$ with $|x - y| < \delta$.

- **Definition 25.4.** Let f be a real valued function defined on $S \subset \mathbb{R}$. A function \tilde{f} defined on \tilde{S} is said to be an extension of f if $S \subset \tilde{S}$ and $\tilde{f}(x) = f(x)$ for all $x \in S$.

- **Definition 26.1.** Let f be a real-valued function defined on $S \subset \mathbb{R}$, and let $a \in \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty, -\infty\}$ be the limit of some sequence in S . We write $\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} f(x) = L$ for some $L \in \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty, -\infty\}$ if for every sequence $\{x_n\}$ in S with $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = a$ we have $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n) = L$. In this case, we say "as x tends to a along S , the limit of f exists and is equal to L ."

Propositions

- **Proposition 1.3 (Density of \mathbb{Q}).** If $a, b \in \mathbb{Q}$ with $a < b$, then there exists $c \in \mathbb{Q}$ with $a < c < b$.
- **Proposition 2.3 (Basic properties of $|\cdot|$).** For all $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$, the followings hold.
 - (i) $|a| \geq 0$, and $|a| = 0 \iff a = 0$.
 - (ii) $|-a| = |a|$.
 - (iii) $|ab| = |a||b|$.
 - (iv) $-|a| \leq a \leq |a|$.
- **Proposition 3.5 (Epsilon characterization of sup).** Let $S \subset \mathbb{R}$ be nonempty and bounded from above. A number $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ satisfies $\alpha = \sup S$ if and only if
 - (i) α is an upper bound of S (i.e. $s \leq \alpha$ for all $s \in S$), and
 - (ii) for every $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $s_\varepsilon \in S$ with $s_\varepsilon > \alpha - \varepsilon$. (The elements of S can be arbitrarily closed to α)
- **Proposition 3.6 (Epsilon characterization of inf).** Let $S \subset \mathbb{R}$ be nonempty and bounded from below. A number $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ satisfies

- $\alpha = \inf S$ if and only if
- (i) α is a lower bound of S (i.e. $s \geq \alpha$ for all $s \in S$), and
 - (ii) for every $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $s_\varepsilon \in S$ with $s_\varepsilon < \alpha + \varepsilon$. (The elements of S can be arbitrarily closed to α)

- **Proposition 12.3.** Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence.
 1. If the sequence $\{s_n\}$ is not bounded from above, it has a strictly increasing subsequence diverging to $+\infty$.
 2. If the sequence $\{s_n\}$ is not bounded from below, it has a strictly decreasing subsequence diverging to $-\infty$.
- **Proposition 12.4.** Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence of real numbers and let $t \in \mathbb{R}$. Suppose that for every $\varepsilon > 0$, the set

$$E_\varepsilon := \{n \in \mathbb{N} \mid |s_n - t| < \varepsilon\}$$

is infinite. Then there exists a subsequence $\{s_{n_k}\}$ with $s_{n_k} \rightarrow t$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

Theorems

- **Theorem 2.4 (Triangle Inequality).** For all $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$, it holds that

$$|a + b| \leq |a| + |b|.$$

- **Corollary 2.5 (Distance triangle inequality).** For all $a, b, c \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$\text{dist}(a, c) \leq \text{dist}(a, b) + \text{dist}(b, c).$$

- **Corollary 2.6 (Reverse triangle inequality).** For all $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$||a| - |b|| \leq |a - b|.$$

- **Corollary 2.7.** For any $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $a_1, \dots, a_n \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$\left| \sum_{k=1}^n a_k \right| \leq \sum_{k=1}^n |a_k|.$$

- **Lemma 3.7.** Let $S \subset \mathbb{R}$ be nonempty. Then

$$\sup S = -\inf(-S),$$

where $-S := \{-s \mid s \in S\}$. Consequently, $\inf S = -\sup(-S)$.

- **Corollary 4.1 (Infimum exists).** Every nonempty subset $S \subset \mathbb{R}$ that is bounded from below has an infimum in \mathbb{R} .
- **Corollary 4.2 (Archimedean property of \mathbb{R}).** If $a > 0$ and $b > 0$, then there exists some $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $na > b$.
- **Lemma 4.3.** If $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ and $b - a > 1$ then there is an integer m such that $a < m < b$.
- **Corollary 4.4 (\mathbb{Q} is dense in \mathbb{R}).** If $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ and $a < b$ then there is a rational $\frac{m}{n} \in \mathbb{Q}$ such that $a < \frac{m}{n} < b$.
- **Corollary 4.5 (Nested interval property).** Let $\{a_n\}$ be increasing and $\{b_n\}$ be decreasing with $a_n \leq b_n$ for all n . Then the closed intervals $[a_n, b_n]$ have nonempty intersection:

$$\bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} [a_n, b_n] \neq \emptyset.$$

- **Theorem 5.8.** If a sequence converges, then its limit is unique.
- **Lemma 6.1.** If $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} s_n = s$ for some $s \in \mathbb{R}$, then $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} |s_n| = |s|$.
- **Theorem 6.2 (Convergent sequences are bounded).** If $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} s_n = s$ for some $s \in \mathbb{R}$, then sequence $\{s_n\}$ is bounded, i.e. there exists some $M > 0$ such that $|s_n| \leq M$ for all n .
- **Lemma 6.6 (Squeeze Lemma).** Let $\{a_n\}, \{b_n\}$, and $\{s_n\}$ be three sequences such that $a_n \leq s_n \leq b_n$ for all n . If $\lim a_n = \lim b_n = s$, then $\lim s_n = s$.
- **Theorem 7.1 (Scalar Multiple).** Let $\{s_n\}$ converge to a real number. Then $\lim(a \cdot s_n) = a \cdot \lim s_n$ for every $a \in \mathbb{R}$.

- **Theorem 7.2 (Addition).** Let $\{s_n\}$ and $\{t_n\}$ both converge to some real numbers. Then $\lim(s_n + t_n) = \lim s_n + \lim t_n$.
- **Theorem 7.3 (Multiplication).** Let $\{s_n\}$ and $\{t_n\}$ both converge to some real numbers. Then $\lim(s_n t_n) = (\lim s_n)(\lim t_n)$.
- **Theorem 7.4 (Division).** Let $\{s_n\}$ and $\{t_n\}$ both converge to some real numbers. Assume that $s_n \neq 0$ for all n and $\lim s_n$ is non-zero. Then

$$\lim \frac{t_n}{s_n} = \frac{\lim t_n}{\lim s_n}.$$

- **Theorem 7.5 (Some Basic Sequential Limits).** The following statements hold.

1. $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^p} = 0$ for $p > 0$.
2. $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a^n = 0$ if $|a| < 1$.
3. $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n^{1/n} = 1$.
4. $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a^{1/n} = 1$ for $a > 0$.

- **Theorem 8.3.** Let $\{s_n\}$ and $\{t_n\}$ be two sequences such that $\lim s_n = +\infty$ and $\inf\{t_n \mid n > N_0\} > 0$ for some $N_0 \in \mathbb{N}$. Then $\lim s_n t_n = +\infty$.

- **Theorem 8.5.** For a sequence $\{s_n\}$ of positive real numbers, we have $\lim s_n = +\infty$ if and only if $\lim \frac{1}{s_n} = 0$.

- **Theorem 9.3.** All bounded monotone sequences converge.
- **Theorem 9.6.** If $\{s_n\}$ is an unbounded increasing sequence, then $\lim s_n = +\infty$. Consequently, if $\{s_n\}$ is an unbounded decreasing sequence, then $\lim s_n = -\infty$.

- **Theorem 9.9.** Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence of real numbers.
 1. If $\lim s_n$ exists (as a real number, $+\infty$ or $-\infty$), then $\liminf s_n = \lim s_n = \limsup s_n$.
 2. If $\liminf s_n = \limsup s_n = A$ ($A \in \mathbb{R}$ or $A = \infty$ or $A = -\infty$), then $\lim s_n$ exists and $\lim s_n = A$.

- **Lemma 10.2.** Convergent sequences are Cauchy sequences.
- **Lemma 10.3.** Cauchy sequences are bounded.
- **Theorem 10.4.** A sequence is convergent if and only if it is Cauchy.

- **Theorem 12.6.** If $\{s_n\}$ converges to $s \in \mathbb{R}$, then every subsequence $\{s_{n_k}\}$ also converges to s .

- **Theorem 13.1 (Bolzano-Weierstrass Theorem).** Every bounded sequence has a convergent subsequence.

- **Lemma 13.2.** Every sequence has a monotonic subsequence.
- **Theorem 13.3.** Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence. There exists a monotonic subsequence whose limit is $\limsup s_n$ and there exists a monotonic subsequence whose limit is $\liminf s_n$.

- **Lemma 13.4.** Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence, and let $\{s_{n_k}\}$ be a subsequence of $\{s_n\}$ such that $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} s_{n_k}$ exists. Then $\limsup s_n \geq \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} s_{n_k} \geq \liminf s_n$.

- **Theorem 14.1.** If $\{s_n\}$ converges to a number $s > 0$ and $\{t_n\}$ is any sequence, then

$$\limsup s_n t_n = s \cdot \limsup t_n.$$

Here we are adopting the convention that $s \cdot (+\infty) = +\infty$ and $s \cdot (-\infty) = -\infty$ for $s > 0$.

- **Theorem 14.2.** Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence of nonzero real numbers. Then

$$\liminf \left| \frac{s_{n+1}}{s_n} \right| \leq \liminf |s_n|^{1/n} \leq \limsup |s_n|^{1/n} \leq \limsup \left| \frac{s_{n+1}}{s_n} \right|.$$

- **Corollary 14.3.** If $\lim \left| \frac{s_{n+1}}{s_n} \right| = L$ exists, then $\lim |s_n|^{1/n} = L$ exists.

- **Theorem 15.2.** If a series $\sum a_k$ converges, then $\lim a_k = 0$.

- **Theorem 15.4.** A series converges if and only if it satisfies the Cauchy criterion.

- **Theorem 16.2 (Comparison Test).** Let $\sum a_k$ be a series where $a_k \geq 0$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

1. If $\sum a_k$ converges and $|b_k| \leq a_k$ for all k , then $\sum b_k$ converges.
2. If $\sum a_k = +\infty$ and $b_k \geq a_k$ for all k , then $\sum b_k = +\infty$.

- **Corollary 16.3.** Absolutely convergent series are convergent.

- **Theorem 17.1 (Root Test).** Let $\sum a_k$ be a series and let $\alpha = \limsup |a_k|^{1/k}$. The series $\sum a_k$

1. converges absolutely if $\alpha < 1$,
2. diverges if $\alpha > 1$.

- **Theorem 17.3 (Ratio Test).** A series $\sum a_k$ of nonzero terms

1. converges if $\limsup \left| \frac{a_{k+1}}{a_k} \right| < 1$,
2. diverges if $\liminf \left| \frac{a_{k+1}}{a_k} \right| > 1$.

- **Theorem 18.3 (Integral test).** Let $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k$ be a series. Suppose there is a locally integrable, nonnegative, decreasing function f on $[1, \infty)$ such that $f(k) = a_k$ for all $k = 1, 2, \dots$. Then

1. $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k$ diverges to $+\infty$ if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_1^n f(x) dx = +\infty$.
2. $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k$ converges if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_1^n f(x) dx$ is finite.

- **Theorem 19.2 (Alternating Series Test).** If $\{a_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$ is a non-negative decreasing sequence with $\lim a_k = 0$, then the alternating series $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{k+1} a_k$ converges to a real number s . Moreover, the partial sums $s_n = \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k+1} a_k$ satisfy

$$|s - s_n| < a_n \quad \text{for all } n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

- **Theorem 20.3 (Equivalent definition of pointwise continuity).** Let f be a real valued function defined on $S \subset \mathbb{R}$. Then f is continuous at $x_0 \in S$ if and only if

$$\forall \epsilon > 0, \exists \delta > 0 \text{ such that } |f(x) - f(x_0)| < \epsilon \\ \text{for all } x \in S \text{ with } |x - x_0| < \delta.$$

- **Theorem 21.1.** Let f and g be real valued functions continuous at $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}$. Then

1. $f + g$ is continuous at x_0 .
2. fg is continuous at x_0 .
3. $\frac{f}{g}$ is continuous at x_0 if $g(x_0) \neq 0$.

- **Theorem 21.2.** If f is continuous at x_0 and g is continuous at $f(x_0)$ then $g \circ f$ is continuous at x_0 .

- **Corollary 21.3.** Let f and g be real valued functions continuous at x_0 , and let $c \in \mathbb{R}$ be a constant. Then cf , $|f|$, and $f - g$ are also continuous at x_0 .

- **Corollary 21.4.** Let f and g be real valued functions continuous at x_0 . Then $\max\{f, g\}$ and $\min\{f, g\}$ are also continuous at x_0 .

- **Theorem 22.1 (Boundedness).** Let f be a continuous real-valued function on a closed interval $[a, b]$. Then f is bounded, i.e. there exists some $M > 0$ such that $|f(x)| \leq M$ for all $x \in [a, b]$.

- **Theorem 22.3 (Extremal Values are achieved).** Let f be a continuous real-valued function on a closed interval $[a, b]$. Then f attains its maximum and minimum values on $[a, b]$, i.e. there exist $x_0, y_0 \in [a, b]$ such that $f(x_0) \leq f(x) \leq f(y_0)$ for all $x \in [a, b]$.

- **Theorem 22.5 (Intermediate Value Theorem).** If f is a continuous real-valued function on a closed interval $[a, b]$, then for any y in between $f(a)$ and $f(b)$, i.e. $f(a) < y < f(b)$ or $f(b) < y < f(a)$, there exists at least one $x \in (a, b)$ such that $f(x) = y$.

- **Corollary 22.6.** If f is continuous on an interval I , then the set $f(I) = \{f(x) \mid x \in I\}$ is also an interval.

- **Theorem 23.3.** Let f be a one-to-one continuous function on an interval I . Then f is either strictly increasing or strictly decreasing on I .

- **Theorem 23.4.** If g is a strictly increasing function on an interval J such that $g(J)$ is an interval I , then g is continuous on J .

- **Theorem 23.5 (Inverse Function Theorem).** Let f be a continuous strictly increasing function on some interval I . Then its inverse function f^{-1} is a continuous strictly increasing function on the interval $J = f(I)$.

- **Theorem 24.8 (Heine-Cantor Theorem).** If f is continuous on a closed interval $[a, b]$ then f is uniformly continuous on $[a, b]$.

- **Theorem 24.9.** Let f be a continuous function on an interval I . [I may be bounded or unbounded]. Let I° be the interval obtained by removing from I any endpoints that happen to be in I . If f is differentiable on I° and f' is bounded on I° , then f is uniformly continuous on I .

- **Theorem 25.1.** If f is uniformly continuous on a set S and $\{s_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in S , then $\{f(s_n)\}$ is a Cauchy sequence.

- **Theorem 25.5.** Let $f : (a, b) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a real-valued function. Then f is uniformly continuous on (a, b) if and only if f can be extended to a continuous function \tilde{f} on $[a, b]$.

- **Theorem 26.6.** Let f be a function defined on a subset S of \mathbb{R} and let a be a real number that is the limit of some sequence in S , and let L be a real number. Then $\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} f(x) = L$ if and only if

$$\forall \epsilon > 0, \exists \delta > 0 \text{ such that } |f(x) - L| < \epsilon \\ \text{for all } x \in S \text{ with } |x - a| < \delta.$$

- **Theorem 27.1.** Let f_1 and f_2 be functions for which the limits $\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} f_1(x) = L_1$ and $\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} f_2(x) = L_2$ exist and are finite. Then

1. $\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} (f_1 + f_2)(x) = L_1 + L_2$.
2. $\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} (f_1 f_2)(x) = L_1 L_2$.
3. If $L_2 \neq 0$ and $f_2(x) \neq 0$ for all $x \in S$, then $\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} \left(\frac{f_1}{f_2} \right)(x) = \frac{L_1}{L_2}$.

- **Theorem 27.2.** Let f be a function for which $\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} f(x) = L$ exists and is finite. If g is a function defined on $f(S) \cup \{L\}$ and is continuous at L , then $\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} (g \circ f)(x) = g(L)$.

- **Theorem 27.5.** Let f be a function defined on $J \setminus \{a\}$ for some open interval J containing a . Then $\lim_{x \rightarrow a} f(x)$ exists if and only if the limits $\lim_{x \rightarrow a^-} f(x)$ and $\lim_{x \rightarrow a^+} f(x)$ both exist and are equal, in which case all three limits are equal.

Not Required to Prove

- Lecture 4 corollaries
- Theorem 7.5
- Theorem 9.9
- Theorem 10.4

- Lecture 14 proofs
- Theorem 23.3
- Theorem 23.4
- Theorem 23.5

- Theorem 24.9
- Theorem 25.5
- Lecture 26 proofs
- Lecture 27 proofs

Ch. 3.4 Uniform Continuity

Lemma / Corollary / Definition / Examples	Description
Uniformly Continuous (UC) (Definition 3.4.1)	Let $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ be a set and let $f: A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function. The function f is uniformly continuous if for each $\epsilon > 0$, there is some $\delta > 0$ such that $x, y \in A$ and $ x - y < \delta$ imply $ f(x) - f(y) < \epsilon$.
Logical Form of UC	$(\forall \epsilon > 0) (\exists \delta > 0) (\forall x \in A) (\forall y \in A) [x - y < \delta \rightarrow f(x) - f(y) < \epsilon]$ The order of the quantifiers is crucial. Applies where we can find δ that depends only upon ϵ , and not c .
UC \rightarrow C (Lemma 3.4.2)	Let $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ be a set and let $f: A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function. If f is uniformly continuous, then f is continuous.
Example 3.4.3	(1) $f(x) = mx + b \rightarrow$ Is UC (2) $g(x) = 1/x$ where $x \in \mathbb{R} - \{0\} \rightarrow$ Is not UC (3) $g(x) = 1/x$ where $x \in (1, \infty) \rightarrow$ Is UC
Close Bounded Interval C \rightarrow UC (Theorem 3.4.4)	Let $C \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ be a <u>closed bounded interval</u> , and let $f: C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function. If f is continuous, then f is uniformly continuous.
UC \rightarrow Bounded (Theorem 3.4.5)	Let $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ be a non-empty set and let $f: A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function. Suppose that A is bounded. If f is uniformly continuous, then f is bounded.
C \rightarrow Bounded (Corollary 3.4.6)	Let $C \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ be a closed bounded interval and let $f: C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function. If f is continuous, then f is bounded.

Ch. 3.5 Two Important Theorems

Axiom / Theorem / Lemma / Definition	Description
<p>Extreme Value Theorem: Min. and Max. Exist (Theorem 3.5.1)</p>	<p>Let $C \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ be a closed bounded interval and let $f: C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function. Suppose that f is continuous. Then there are $x_{\min}, x_{\max} \in C$ such that $f(x_{\min}) \leq f(x) \leq f(x_{\max})$ for all $x \in C$.</p>
<p>Intermediate Value Theorem (Theorem 3.5.2)</p>	<p>Let $[a,b] \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ be a closed bounded interval, and let $f: [a,b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function. Suppose that f is continuous. Let $r \in \mathbb{R}$. If r is strictly between $f(a)$ and $f(b)$, then there is some $c \in (a,b)$ such that $f(c) = r$. We can assume $f(a) < r < f(b)$.</p>
<p>Contrapositive for a Proof (Lemma 3.5.3)</p>	<p>Let F be an ordered field. Suppose that F does not satisfy the Least Upper Bound Property. Let $A \subseteq F$ be a non-empty set such that A is bounded above, but A has no least upper bound. Let $a \in A$, and let $b \in F$ be an upper bound of A. Let $Q = \{x \in [a,b] \mid x \text{ is an upper bound of } A\}$ and $P = [a,b] - Q$.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> $P \cup Q = [a,b]$ and $P \cap Q = \emptyset$. $a < b$, and $A \cap [a,b] \subseteq P$, and $a \in P$, and $b \in Q$. If $x \in P$ and $z \in Q$, then $x < z$. If $x \in P$, then there is some $y \in P$ such that $x < y$. If $z \in Q$, then there is some $w \in Q$ such that $w < z$. The set P does not have a least upper bound, and the set Q does not have a greatest lower bound.
<p>Theorem 3.5.4</p>	<p>The following are equivalent.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> The Least Upper Bound Property. The Greatest Lower Bound Property. The Heine–Borel Theorem. The Extreme Value Theorem. The Intermediate Value Theorem.

KEY DEFINITIONS, THEOREMS, AND PROOF TOOLS

Definitions to know verbatim

- *Sequence limit:* $s_n \rightarrow s$ iff for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists N such that $n \geq N \Rightarrow |s_n - s| < \varepsilon$.
- *Infinite limit of a sequence:* $s_n \rightarrow +\infty$ iff for every $M > 0$ there exists N such that $n \geq N \Rightarrow s_n > M$.
- *Supremum:* $\alpha = \sup S$ iff (i) $s \leq \alpha$ for all $s \in S$ and (ii) for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists $s_\varepsilon \in S$ with $\alpha - \varepsilon < s_\varepsilon \leq \alpha$.
- *Infimum:* $\beta = \inf S$ iff (i) $\beta \leq s$ for all $s \in S$ and (ii) for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists $s_\varepsilon \in S$ with $\beta \leq s_\varepsilon < \beta + \varepsilon$.
- *Cauchy sequence:* $\{s_n\}$ is Cauchy iff for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists N such that $m, n \geq N \Rightarrow |s_n - s_m| < \varepsilon$.
- *Continuity at a :* f is continuous at a iff for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists $\delta > 0$ such that $|x - a| < \delta \Rightarrow |f(x) - f(a)| < \varepsilon$.
- *Sequential continuity:* f is continuous at a iff $x_n \rightarrow a$ implies $f(x_n) \rightarrow f(a)$.
- *Uniform continuity on E :* for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists $\delta > 0$ such that for all $x, y \in E$, $|x - y| < \delta \Rightarrow |f(x) - f(y)| < \varepsilon$.
- *Series convergence:* $\sum a_n$ converges iff the partial sums $s_n = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k$ converge.

Essential theorem statements

- *Completeness axiom:* every nonempty subset of \mathbb{R} that is bounded above has a supremum.
- *Archimedean property:* if $a, b > 0$, then $na > b$ for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$.
- *Density of \mathbb{Q} :* if $a < b$, then there exists $q \in \mathbb{Q}$ with $a < q < b$.
- *Nested intervals theorem:* if $[a_n, b_n]$ are nested closed intervals, then $\bigcap_n [a_n, b_n] \neq \emptyset$; if $b_n - a_n \rightarrow 0$, the intersection is a single point.
- *Monotone convergence theorem:* an increasing sequence bounded above converges, and its limit is the supremum of its range.
- *Bolzano–Weierstrass:* every bounded sequence in \mathbb{R} has a convergent subsequence.
- *Cauchy \Leftrightarrow convergence in \mathbb{R} :* a sequence in \mathbb{R} converges iff it is Cauchy.
- *Geometric series:* $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} r^n = \frac{1}{1-r}$ for $|r| < 1$.
- *p -series:* $\sum 1/n^p$ converges iff $p > 1$.
- *Cauchy criterion for series:* $\sum a_n$ converges iff for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists N such that $m > n \geq N \Rightarrow |\sum_{k=n+1}^m a_k| < \varepsilon$.
- *Comparison test:* if $0 \leq a_n \leq b_n$ eventually and $\sum b_n$ converges, then $\sum a_n$ converges.
- *Ratio test:* if $\lim |a_{n+1}/a_n| = L < 1$, then $\sum a_n$ converges absolutely; if $L > 1$, it diverges.
- *Root test:* if $\limsup \sqrt[n]{|a_n|} = L < 1$, then $\sum a_n$ converges absolutely; if $L > 1$, it diverges.
- *Integral test:* for positive decreasing f with $a_n = f(n)$, $\sum a_n$ and $\int f$ have the same convergence behavior.
- *Alternating series test:* if $a_n \downarrow 0$, then $\sum (-1)^{n+1} a_n$ converges and $|s - s_n| \leq a_{n+1}$.
- *EVT:* if f is continuous on $[a, b]$, then f is bounded and attains its max and min.
- *IVT:* if f is continuous on $[a, b]$ and L lies between $f(a)$ and $f(b)$, then $f(c) = L$ for some $c \in [a, b]$.
- *Fixed point theorem on $[a, b]$:* if $f : [a, b] \rightarrow [a, b]$ is continuous, then $f(c) = c$ for some $c \in [a, b]$.
- *Inverse theorem on intervals:* a continuous strictly monotone function on an interval has a continuous inverse on its image.
- *Heine–Cantor:* continuous on a compact interval $[a, b]$ implies uniformly continuous.
- *Cauchy image theorem:* uniformly continuous maps send Cauchy sequences to Cauchy sequences.
- *Extension theorem:* a uniformly continuous $f : E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ extends uniquely to a continuous function on \overline{E} .
- *Subsequence theorem:* if $s_n \rightarrow s$, then every subsequence $s_{n_k} \rightarrow s$.

- *Limit laws:* if $a_n \leq b_n$ for all n , $a_n \rightarrow a$, and $b_n \rightarrow b$, then $a \leq b$ and if $a_n \rightarrow a$ and $b_n \rightarrow b$, then $a_n + b_n \rightarrow a + b$ and $a_n b_n \rightarrow ab$.
- *Convergent sequences are bounded:* if $s_n \rightarrow s$, then $\{s_n\}$ is bounded.
- *Uniqueness of limits:* if $s_n \rightarrow s$ and $s_n \rightarrow t$, then $s = t$.

Absolute value / ordered field tools

$$|x + y| \leq |x| + |y|, \quad ||x| - |y|| \leq |x - y|.$$

If $0 < b < a$, then multiplying by $1/(ab) > 0$ gives $1/a < 1/b$.

Exam proof templates

- *To prove $\alpha = \sup S$:* show α is an upper bound and approximate it from below using the ε -characterization.
- *To prove convergence directly:* start with $\varepsilon > 0$ and solve the target inequality for n .
- *To prove divergence:* find two subsequences with different limits, or show the sequence is unbounded/oscillatory.
- *To use monotone convergence:* prove monotone + bounded, then identify the limit by passing to the recursion or by supremum.
- *To prove Cauchy:* estimate $|s_n - s_m|$ for m, n large; split through a common limit if one is known.
- *To analyze a series:* move immediately to the partial sums or to a benchmark series (geometric, $1/n^p$, $1/(n(\log n)^q)$).
- *Comparison checklist:* rational powers \rightarrow compare with $1/n^p$; factorial/exponential \rightarrow ratio/root; logarithms \rightarrow integral test.
- *To prove discontinuity:* choose $x_n \rightarrow a$ (often two sequences) so that $f(x_n)$ fails to approach $f(a)$.
- *To prove not uniformly continuous:* construct x_n, y_n with $|x_n - y_n| \rightarrow 0$ but $|f(x_n) - f(y_n)| \not\rightarrow 0$.
- *Heine–Cantor contradiction pattern:* assume failure of uniform continuity, get $|x_n - y_n| < 1/n$, extract a convergent subsequence, and contradict continuity.
- *Extension pattern:* if $x_n \rightarrow x$ with $x_n \in E$, then $\{x_n\}$ is Cauchy; uniform continuity makes $\{f(x_n)\}$ Cauchy, hence convergent.
- *To construct a sequence approaching $\sup S$:* for each n , choose $x_n \in S$ with $\sup S - \frac{1}{n} < x_n \leq \sup S$.
- *To prove $a_n b_n \rightarrow 0$:* if $a_n \rightarrow 0$ and (b_n) is bounded, use $|a_n b_n| \leq M|a_n|$.
- *To telescope a series:* first rewrite the summand in the form $u_n - u_{n+1}$, then compute the partial sum explicitly.
- *To prove a subsequence fact:* use $n_1 < n_2 < \dots \Rightarrow n_k \geq k$, so large k forces large original index.
- *To prove $a \leq b$ from $a_n \leq b_n$:* assume $a > b$; with $\varepsilon = \frac{a-b}{2}$ large n give $a_n > b_n$.
- *To prove $\sqrt{a_n} \rightarrow \sqrt{a}$:* rationalize $|\sqrt{a_n} - \sqrt{a}| = \frac{|a_n - a|}{\sqrt{a_n} + \sqrt{a}}$, then bound the denominator away from 0 when $a > 0$.

Benchmark examples worth memorizing

- Oscillation with no limit: $(-1)^n$.
- Oscillation with a limit: $\sin n/n \rightarrow 0$ by squeeze.
- Two subsequential limits: $(-1)^n + 1/n$ has $\limsup = 1$, $\liminf = -1$.
- Telescoping: $\sum 1/(n(n+1)) = 1$.
- Borderline logarithms: $\sum 1/(n \log n)$ diverges, $\sum 1/(n(\log n)^2)$ converges.
- Oscillatory discontinuity: $f(x) = \sin(1/x)$ at 0.
- Non-uniform continuity: $1/x$ on $(0, 1]$ or x^2 on \mathbb{R} .
- Supremum approximation: if $s = \sup S$, choose $x_n \in S$ with $s - \frac{1}{n} < x_n \leq s$, then $x_n \rightarrow s$.
- Bounded times convergent: if $a_n \rightarrow 0$ and (b_n) is bounded, then $a_n b_n \rightarrow 0$.
- Positive extension example: $g(x) = x \sin(1/x)$ on $(0, 1]$ extends continuously to $g(0) = 0$.

1. L1–2: induction, ordered fields, absolute value

Key facts. Ordered-field rules preserve inequalities under addition and multiplication by positive numbers. Induction requires a base case and a valid step $P(n) \Rightarrow P(n+1)$. Absolute value satisfies triangle and reverse triangle inequalities.

Canonical example. Prove the finite triangle inequality

$$\left| \sum_{k=1}^n a_k \right| \leq \sum_{k=1}^n |a_k|.$$

Model proof pattern. For $n = 1$ it is equality. Assume the claim for n . Then

$$\left| \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} a_k \right| = \left| \left(\sum_{k=1}^n a_k \right) + a_{n+1} \right| \leq \left| \sum_{k=1}^n a_k \right| + |a_{n+1}| \leq \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} |a_k|.$$

Induction is also the clean way to prove finite geometric sums.

Typical application. Uniqueness of limits: if $s_n \rightarrow s$ and $s_n \rightarrow t$, then

$$|s - t| \leq |s - s_n| + |s_n - t| < \varepsilon$$

for all large n , so $s = t$.

2. L3–4: supremum/infimum, completeness, density, nested intervals

Key facts. Completeness is the source of suprema. To prove a number is the supremum, verify: upper bound + arbitrarily close points from below.

Canonical example. For

$$S = \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{n} : n \in \mathbb{N} \right\},$$

prove $\sup S = 1$.

Model proof pattern. Since $1 - 1/n < 1$ for all n , the number 1 is an upper bound. If $\varepsilon > 0$, choose $n > 1/\varepsilon$; then $1 - 1/n > 1 - \varepsilon$, so no smaller number can be an upper bound. Hence $\sup S = 1$. **Supremum approximation sequence.** More generally, if $s = \sup S$, then for each n one may choose $x_n \in S$ such that

$$s - \frac{1}{n} < x_n \leq s.$$

Then $x_n \rightarrow s$. **Increasing supremum approximation.** Starting from any such x_n , define

$$t_n = \max\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}.$$

Then $t_n \in S$, the sequence t_n is increasing, and $s - \frac{1}{n} < t_n \leq s$, so $t_n \rightarrow s$. **Important patterns.**

- *Archimedean:* if $a, b > 0$, apply completeness to $\{na : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ to show $na > b$ for some n .
- *Density of \mathbb{Q} :* given $a < b$, choose $n > 1/(b - a)$ and an integer m with $na < m < nb$; then $a < m/n < b$.
- *Density of $\mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q}$:* choose n so large that $\sqrt{2}/n < b - a$, then choose $q \in \mathbb{Q}$ with $a - \sqrt{2}/n < q < b - \sqrt{2}/n$. The number $q + \sqrt{2}/n$ is irrational and lies in (a, b) .
- *Nested intervals:* for nested $[a_n, b_n]$, let $\alpha = \sup\{a_n\}$. Then $a_n \leq \alpha \leq b_n$ for every n , so $\alpha \in \bigcap_n [a_n, b_n]$. If $b_n - a_n \rightarrow 0$, then any two points in the intersection must be equal.

Set addition and extrema. If $A, B \subset \mathbb{R}$ are nonempty and bounded, then

$$\sup(A + B) = \sup A + \sup B, \quad \inf(A + B) = \inf A + \inf B.$$

For the supremum, first note $a + b \leq \sup A + \sup B$ for all $a \in A$, $b \in B$. Then use the ε -characterization on A and B with $\varepsilon/2$ to find $a + b > \sup A + \sup B - \varepsilon$. The infimum proof is analogous.

3. L5–8: limits of sequences, squeeze, infinite limits

Key facts. Convergence is an ε - N condition. Infinite limits use an M - N condition. Limit laws reduce algebra to known limits.

Canonical examples.

- $(-1)^n/n \rightarrow 0$: given $\varepsilon > 0$, choose $N > 1/\varepsilon$.
- $\sin n/n \rightarrow 0$: since $-1/n \leq \sin n/n \leq 1/n$ and both sides go to 0, squeeze applies.
- $\frac{n^3 + 2}{n^2 + 1} \rightarrow +\infty$: for $n \geq 1$,

$$\frac{n^3 + 2}{n^2 + 1} \geq \frac{n^3}{2n^2} = \frac{n}{2} \rightarrow \infty.$$

Model proof pattern. Start with the target inequality and solve for n . Example: to show $1/n < \varepsilon$, require $n > 1/\varepsilon$. For rational functions with finite limits, divide by the highest power of n . **Useful product lemma.** If $a_n \rightarrow 0$ and (b_n) is bounded, then $a_n b_n \rightarrow 0$. Indeed, if $|b_n| \leq M$ for all n , then $|a_n b_n| \leq M|a_n| \rightarrow 0$. **Reciprocal criterion.** For positive terms,

$$a_n \rightarrow +\infty \iff \frac{1}{a_n} \rightarrow 0.$$

Indeed, $a_n > M$ eventually iff $\frac{1}{a_n} < \frac{1}{M}$ eventually. **Direct divergence from the definition.** To show $(-1)^n$ does not converge, assume $(-1)^n \rightarrow L$. With $\varepsilon = 1$, all large even and odd terms would satisfy

$$|1 - L| < 1, \quad |-1 - L| < 1.$$

But then

$$2 = |1 - (-1)| \leq |1 - L| + |L + 1| < 2,$$

a contradiction.

Warning example. Oscillation alone does not imply divergence: $\sin n$ need not settle down, but $\sin n/n \rightarrow 0$ because the oscillation is trapped by a shrinking bound.

4. L9–10: monotone convergence and Cauchy sequences

Key facts. Increasing + bounded above \Rightarrow convergent. In \mathbb{R} , Cauchy and convergent are equivalent.

Canonical example. Let $x_1 = 1$ and $x_{n+1} = \sqrt{2 + x_n}$. Prove $x_n \rightarrow 2$.

Model proof pattern.

1. Show $x_n < 2$ for all n by induction.
2. Show $x_n \leq x_{n+1}$ by induction: first $x_1 = 1 \leq \sqrt{3} = x_2$. If $x_n \leq x_{n+1}$, then

$$\sqrt{2 + x_n} \leq \sqrt{2 + x_{n+1}}.$$

3. Apply monotone convergence.
4. If $x_n \rightarrow L$, pass to the recursion:

$$L = \sqrt{2 + L} \implies L^2 - L - 2 = 0 \implies L = 2$$

(since $L > 0$).

Cauchy proof patterns.

- *Convergent \Rightarrow Cauchy:* split through the limit,

$$|s_n - s_m| \leq |s_n - s| + |s_m - s|.$$

- *Cauchy \Rightarrow bounded:* choose N so that $|s_n - s_N| < 1$ for $n \geq N$, then absorb the first finitely many terms into a maximum.
- *Cauchy \Rightarrow convergent:* use boundedness + Bolzano–Weierstrass to get a convergent subsequence, then use the Cauchy property to force the whole sequence to have the same limit.

Successive-difference criterion. If

$$|s_{n+1} - s_n| \leq r_n$$

and $\sum r_n$ converges, then $\{s_n\}$ is Cauchy. Indeed, for $m > n$,

$$|s_m - s_n| \leq \sum_{k=n}^{m-1} |s_{k+1} - s_k| \leq \sum_{k=n}^{m-1} r_k,$$

and the tail on the right goes to 0. In particular, the bound $|s_{n+1} - s_n| < 2^{-n}$ forces convergence. **Weakened bound counterexample.** The harmonic partial sums

$$H_n = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k}$$

satisfy $H_{n+1} - H_n = \frac{1}{n+1} < \frac{1}{n}$, but $\{H_n\}$ is not Cauchy because $\sum 1/n$ diverges. **Integer-valued convergence.** If $a_n \in \mathbb{Z}$ for all n and $a_n \rightarrow L$, then the sequence is eventually constant: choose N so that $|a_n - L| < 1/2$ for $n \geq N$. The interval $(L-1/2, L+1/2)$ contains at most one integer, so all large a_n are equal. **Squares of monotone sequences.** If $\{u_n\}$ is monotone, then $u_n \rightarrow L$ implies $u_n^2 \rightarrow L^2$ by limit laws. Conversely, if u_n^2 converges, then $\{u_n^2\}$ is bounded, so $\{|u_n|\}$ is bounded and hence $\{u_n\}$ is bounded. A bounded monotone sequence converges. Without monotonicity this fails: $v_n = (-1)^n$ has $v_n^2 = 1$ for all n , but $\{v_n\}$ does not converge.

5. L12–14: subsequences, diagonalization, BW, limsup/liminf Key facts. Every bounded sequence has a convergent subsequence. A sequence converges to L iff every subsequence converges to L . The numbers $\limsup s_n$ and $\liminf s_n$ are the largest and smallest subsequential limits.

Canonical examples.

- $(-1)^n$ does not converge because the subsequences $s_{2k} = 1$ and $s_{2k+1} = -1$ have different limits.
- For $s_n = (-1)^n + 1/n$,

$$s_{2k} = 1 + \frac{1}{2k} \rightarrow 1, \quad s_{2k+1} = -1 + \frac{1}{2k+1} \rightarrow -1.$$

Hence $\limsup s_n = 1$ and $\liminf s_n = -1$.

Subsequence pattern. For alternating sequences, the first subsequences to test are usually the even and odd ones:

$$x_{2k}, \quad x_{2k+1}.$$

This is the fastest way to detect different subsequential limits. **Diagonalization pattern.** If for each k there are infinitely many n with $|x_n - a| < 1/k$, choose $n_1 < n_2 < \dots$ so that $|x_{n_k} - a| < 1/k$. Then $x_{n_k} \rightarrow a$. This is the standard “choose one term from each tighter neighborhood” method.

Fast criterion. If a bounded sequence has only one possible subsequential limit L , then the whole sequence converges to L . **Enumeration trick.** If $\{r_n\}$ enumerates \mathbb{Q} , then one can choose a subsequence tending to $+\infty$: after choosing $n_1 < \dots < n_k$, pick an integer $m > k$ not appearing among r_1, \dots, r_{n_k} . Since every rational appears somewhere in the enumeration, there exists $n_{k+1} > n_k$ with $r_{n_{k+1}} = m$. Then $r_{n_k} \geq k - 1$ for all $k \geq 2$, so $r_{n_k} \rightarrow +\infty$. **Sign identity.** The subsequential limits of $\{-s_n\}$ are exactly the numbers $-L$ where L is a subsequential limit of $\{s_n\}$. Therefore

$$\liminf s_n = -\limsup(-s_n).$$

Cesàro means. If

$$\sigma_n = \frac{s_1 + \dots + s_n}{n}$$

and $s_n \rightarrow s$, then $\sigma_n \rightarrow s$. Write

$$\sigma_n - s = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n (s_k - s).$$

Choose N so that $|s_k - s| < \varepsilon$ for $k \geq N$; the first $N - 1$ terms contribute $o(1)$, and the remaining terms have average size at most ε . The converse fails: for $s_n = (-1)^n$, one has $\sigma_n \rightarrow 0$ although s_n does not converge.

6. L15–16: series basics, geometric, telescoping, p-series, Cauchy criterion Key facts. Always rewrite a series using partial sums $s_n = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k$. If $\sum a_n$ converges, then $a_n = s_n - s_{n-1} \rightarrow 0$. The geometric series and p -series are the main benchmarks.

Canonical examples.

- *Geometric:*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} r^n = \frac{1}{1-r} \quad (|r| < 1).$$

- *Telescoping:*

$$\frac{1}{n(n+1)} = \frac{1}{n} - \frac{1}{n+1},$$

so

$$\sum_{n=1}^N \frac{1}{n(n+1)} = \sum_{n=1}^N \left(\frac{1}{n} - \frac{1}{n+1} \right) = 1 - \frac{1}{N+1}.$$

Hence

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n(n+1)} = 1.$$

- *Counterexample to “ $a_n \rightarrow 0$ implies convergence”:* $\sum 1/n$ diverges although $1/n \rightarrow 0$.

Model proof pattern. For telescoping, compute the partial sum explicitly and let $N \rightarrow \infty$. For series proofs, the Cauchy criterion says: tails

$$\sum_{k=n+1}^m a_k$$

must become arbitrarily small. **Bounded coefficients preserve absolute convergence.** If $\sum |a_n|$ converges and $|b_n| \leq M$ for all n , then

$$|a_n b_n| \leq M |a_n|,$$

so $\sum |a_n b_n|$ converges by comparison. Hence $\sum a_n b_n$ converges. **Useful constructions involving a_n and a_n^2 .**

- If $a_n = 1/n$, then $\sum a_n$ diverges but $\sum a_n^2 = \sum 1/n^2$ converges.
- If $a_n = (-1)^{n+1}/\sqrt{n}$, then $\sum a_n$ converges by the alternating-series test, but $\sum a_n^2 = \sum 1/n$ diverges.

7. L17–19: comparison, ratio/root, integral, alternating Decision tree. Positive rational functions \rightarrow compare with $1/n^p$. Factorials/exponentials \rightarrow ratio or root. Logarithmic denominators \rightarrow integral test. Alternating signs with decreasing magnitude \rightarrow alternating-series test.

Canonical examples.

- *Comparison:*

$$0 \leq \frac{n}{n^3 + 1} \leq \frac{1}{n^2},$$

so $\sum n/(n^3 + 1)$ converges.

- *Borderline logarithms:*

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n \log n} \text{ diverges,} \quad \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n(\log n)^2} \text{ converges,}$$

by the integral test.

- *Ratio test:* for $a_n = (n!)^2/(2n)!$,

$$\frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} = \frac{(n+1)^2}{(2n+2)(2n+1)} \rightarrow \frac{1}{4} < 1,$$

so the series converges absolutely.

- *Root test:* for $a_n = \left(\frac{n}{n+1}\right)^{n^2}$,

$$\sqrt[n]{a_n} = \left(\frac{n}{n+1}\right)^n \rightarrow e^{-1} < 1,$$

so the series converges absolutely. **Root test signal.** If the exponent contains n^2 or another growing power of n , the root test is often the fastest choice.

- *Alternating:*

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+1} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$$

converges by AST but not absolutely since $\sum 1/\sqrt{n}$ diverges.

Error estimate. For an alternating series with decreasing $a_n \rightarrow 0$,

$$|s - s_n| \leq a_{n+1}.$$

That gives quick numerical bounds. **Decreasing positive terms of a convergent series.** If a_n is decreasing, positive, and $\sum a_n$ converges, then

$$\frac{n}{2} a_n \leq \sum_{k=\lfloor n/2 \rfloor + 1}^n a_k.$$

The right-hand side is a tail of a convergent series, so it goes to 0. Hence $na_n \rightarrow 0$.

8. L20–21: continuity and discontinuity by sequences Key facts. For exam proofs, sequential continuity is often fastest. To prove discontinuity, produce a bad sequence (or two bad sequences) approaching the point.

Canonical examples.

- *Continuity of $|x|$:* if $x_n \rightarrow x_0$, then

$$||x_n| - |x_0|| \leq |x_n - x_0| \rightarrow 0.$$

- *Oscillatory discontinuity:* define $f(0) = 0$ and $f(x) = \sin(1/x)$ for $x \neq 0$. Set

$$x_n = \frac{1}{\pi/2 + 2\pi n}, \quad y_n = \frac{1}{3\pi/2 + 2\pi n}.$$

Then $x_n \rightarrow 0$, $y_n \rightarrow 0$, but $f(x_n) = 1$ and $f(y_n) = -1$. Hence f is not continuous at 0.

Model proof pattern. For sums/products/compositions, pass to sequences and use limit laws. For discontinuity, aim for image limits that disagree or fail to equal $f(a)$. **Rational/irrational test case.** For

$$h(x) = \begin{cases} x, & x \in \mathbb{Q}, \\ 0, & x \notin \mathbb{Q}, \end{cases}$$

the only continuity point is 0. If $a \neq 0$, choose $r_n \in \mathbb{Q}$ and $s_n \notin \mathbb{Q}$ with $r_n \rightarrow a$ and $s_n \rightarrow a$. Then $h(r_n) \rightarrow a$ while $h(s_n) \rightarrow 0$, so h is discontinuous at a . At 0, both rational and irrational inputs near 0 have images near 0.

9. L22–23: EVT, IVT, fixed point theorem, inverse continuity Key facts. Continuous functions on closed intervals are bounded and attain extrema (EVT). They take all intermediate values (IVT). These two theorems power existence arguments.

Canonical examples.

- *Odd polynomial has a root:* for large K , $p(-K) < 0 < p(K)$; apply IVT on $[-K, K]$.
- *Fixed point on $[0, 1]$:* if $f : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous, let $g(x) = f(x) - x$. Then $g(0) \geq 0$ and $g(1) \leq 0$, so IVT gives $g(c) = 0$, i.e. $f(c) = c$.
- *Inverse function theorem on intervals:* if f is continuous and strictly monotone on an interval I , then $f^{-1} : f(I) \rightarrow I$ exists and is continuous.

EVT application. If f is continuous on $[a, b]$ and $f(x) \neq 0$ for all $x \in [a, b]$, then $|f|$ attains a minimum value m on $[a, b]$. Since $m \neq 0$, one has

$$|f(x)| \geq m > 0 \quad \text{for all } x \in [a, b].$$

EVT contradiction pattern. If f were unbounded on $[a, b]$, choose $x_n \in [a, b]$ with $|f(x_n)| > n$. A subsequence x_{n_k} converges by BW, and continuity makes $f(x_{n_k})$ bounded near its limit point—contradiction.

Injective \Rightarrow monotone on an interval. A continuous injective function on an interval cannot turn around: if $x < y < z$ and, say, $f(y)$ were above both endpoints, IVT would force a repeated value, contradicting injectivity. **First-zero pattern.** If $f : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuous, $f(0) > 0$, and $f(1) = 0$, let

$$Z = \{x \in [0, 1] : f(x) = 0\}, \quad x_0 = \inf Z.$$

Since $1 \in Z$, the set Z is nonempty. Choose $z_n \in Z$ with $x_0 \leq z_n < x_0 + 1/n$; then $z_n \rightarrow x_0$, so continuity gives $f(x_0) = 0$. If some $y < x_0$ had $f(y) \leq 0$, IVT on $[y, x_0]$ would produce a zero smaller than x_0 . Hence $f(x) > 0$ for all $x \in [0, x_0)$. **Average-value existence from IVT.** Let

$$A = \frac{f(x_1) + \cdots + f(x_n)}{n}.$$

If $m = \min_j f(x_j)$ and $M = \max_j f(x_j)$, then $m \leq A \leq M$. Choose indices p, q with $f(x_p) = m$ and $f(x_q) = M$. Since A lies between $f(x_p)$ and $f(x_q)$, IVT on the interval between x_p and x_q gives z with $f(z) = A$. **Bounded-image fixed point on \mathbb{R} .** If $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is

continuous and $|f(x)| \leq M$ for all x , let $g(x) = f(x) - x$. Then

$$g(-M) = f(-M) + M \geq 0, \quad g(M) = f(M) - M \leq 0.$$

So IVT on $[-M, M]$ gives $g(c) = 0$, hence $f(c) = c$.

10. L24–25: uniform continuity, Heine–Cantor, Cauchy image, extension Key facts. Uniform continuity uses one δ for the whole domain. Compactness often upgrades continuity to uniform continuity.

Canonical examples.

- *Failure of uniform continuity:* $f(x) = 1/x$ on $(0, 1]$ is not uniformly continuous. Take

$$x_n = \frac{1}{n}, \quad y_n = \frac{1}{n+1}.$$

Then $|x_n - y_n| \rightarrow 0$, but

$$|f(x_n) - f(y_n)| = |n - (n+1)| = 1.$$

- *Extension example:* $g(x) = x \sin(1/x)$ on $(0, 1]$ extends continuously to $g(0) = 0$. Hence g is uniformly continuous on $(0, 1]$.
- *Positive example:* \sqrt{x} is uniformly continuous on $[0, \infty)$ because

$$|\sqrt{x} - \sqrt{y}| = \frac{|x - y|}{\sqrt{x} + \sqrt{y}} \leq \sqrt{|x - y|}.$$

Derivative bound \Rightarrow Lipschitz. If $|f'(x)| \leq M$ on $[a, b]$, then for any distinct $x, y \in [a, b]$ the Mean Value Theorem gives a point c between x and y such that

$$\frac{f(x) - f(y)}{x - y} = f'(c).$$

Hence

$$|f(x) - f(y)| \leq M|x - y|.$$

In particular, f is uniformly continuous on $[a, b]$.

Heine–Cantor proof pattern. Assume f is continuous on $[a, b]$ but not uniformly continuous. Then there exist $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ and $x_n, y_n \in [a, b]$ with $|x_n - y_n| < 1/n$ and $|f(x_n) - f(y_n)| \geq \varepsilon_0$. Extract $x_{n_k} \rightarrow x_0$ by BW. Since $|x_{n_k} - y_{n_k}| \rightarrow 0$, also $y_{n_k} \rightarrow x_0$. Continuity gives $|f(x_{n_k}) - f(y_{n_k})| \rightarrow 0$, contradiction. **Periodic continuous functions.** If $f(x + p) = f(x)$ for some $p > 0$, then f is uniformly continuous on \mathbb{R} . Use Heine–Cantor on the compact interval $[-p, 2p]$ to get a δ there, and also require $\delta < p$. For arbitrary $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$ with $|x - y| < \delta$, choose $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ so that $x - kp \in [0, p]$. Then $y - kp \in [-p, 2p]$, and periodicity gives

$$|f(x) - f(y)| = |f(x - kp) - f(y - kp)|.$$

So the same δ works for all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$.

Cauchy image theorem. If f is uniformly continuous and x_n is Cauchy, then for any $\varepsilon > 0$ choose δ from uniform continuity, then choose N so that $|x_n - x_m| < \delta$ for $m, n \geq N$. Hence $|f(x_n) - f(x_m)| < \varepsilon$. **Uniform continuity on bounded sets forces boundedness.** If $S \subset \mathbb{R}$ is bounded and $f : S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is uniformly continuous, then f is bounded on S . Otherwise choose $x_n \in S$ with $|f(x_n)| > n$. Since $\{x_n\}$ is bounded, Bolzano–Weierstrass gives a convergent subsequence x_{n_k} . Then $\{x_{n_k}\}$ is Cauchy, so $\{f(x_{n_k})\}$ is Cauchy by uniform continuity and therefore bounded, contradicting $|f(x_{n_k})| > n_k$.

Extension theorem pattern. If $E \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ and $f : E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is uniformly continuous, define for $x \in \bar{E}$

$$F(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n)$$

where $x_n \in E$ and $x_n \rightarrow x$. This is well defined because any such $\{x_n\}$ is Cauchy, so $\{f(x_n)\}$ is Cauchy and convergent, and two different approximating sequences can be interleaved to show they give the same limit.

11. For completeness only (L26–27, not on the final) Function limits. $\lim_{x \rightarrow a} f(x) = L$ iff for every sequence $x_n \rightarrow a$ with $x_n \neq a$, one has $f(x_n) \rightarrow L$. A two-sided limit exists iff the left and right limits both exist and agree.

Math 142A Proof Atlas / Review Guide

Exam Problem 1

- (a) Prove by induction that $1 + 3 + \cdots + (2n - 1) = n^2$.
 (b) If $a > b > 0$, prove that $1/b > 1/a$.
 (c) Prove that $||x| - |y|| \leq |x - y|$ for all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$.
 (d) Prove that $|\sum_{k=1}^n a_k| \leq \sum_{k=1}^n |a_k|$.

Proof.

- (a) We prove the claim by induction. When
- $n = 1$
- ,

$$1 = 1^2.$$

Assume

$$1 + 3 + \cdots + (2n - 1) = n^2.$$

Then

$$1 + 3 + \cdots + (2n - 1) + (2n + 1) = n^2 + 2n + 1 = (n + 1)^2.$$

Therefore the statement holds for $n + 1$. By induction,

$$1 + 3 + \cdots + (2n - 1) = n^2$$

for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

- (b) Since
- $a > b > 0$
- , we have
- $ab > 0$
- . Multiply the inequality
- $a > b$
- by
- $1/(ab) > 0$
- :

$$\frac{a}{ab} > \frac{b}{ab}.$$

Hence

$$\frac{1}{b} > \frac{1}{a}.$$

- (c) By the triangle inequality,

$$|x| = |x - y + y| \leq |x - y| + |y|,$$

so

$$|x| - |y| \leq |x - y|.$$

Swapping x and y gives

$$|y| - |x| \leq |x - y|.$$

Hence

$$||x| - |y|| \leq |x - y|.$$

- (d) For
- $n = 1$
- it is equality. Assume

$$\left| \sum_{k=1}^n a_k \right| \leq \sum_{k=1}^n |a_k|.$$

Then

$$\left| \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} a_k \right| = \left| \left(\sum_{k=1}^n a_k \right) + a_{n+1} \right| \leq \left| \sum_{k=1}^n a_k \right| + |a_{n+1}| \leq \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} |a_k|.$$

Thus the claim holds for $n + 1$. By induction,

$$\left| \sum_{k=1}^n a_k \right| \leq \sum_{k=1}^n |a_k|.$$

Exam Problem 2

Let

$$S = \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{n} : n \in \mathbb{N} \right\}.$$

- (a) Prove that $\sup S = 1$.
 (b) Prove the Archimedean property: if $a, b > 0$, then $na > b$ for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$.
 (c) If $\alpha < \beta$, prove that there exists $q \in \mathbb{Q}$ with $\alpha < q < \beta$.
 (d) If $\alpha < \beta$, prove that there exists $x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q}$ with $\alpha < x < \beta$.

- (e) If
- $A, B \subset \mathbb{R}$
- are nonempty and bounded, prove

$$\sup(A + B) = \sup A + \sup B, \quad \inf(A + B) = \inf A + \inf B.$$

- (f) If $T \subset \mathbb{R}$ is nonempty and bounded above and $s = \sup T$, construct (x_n) in T with $x_n \rightarrow s$.
 (g) Under the same hypotheses, construct an increasing (t_n) in T with $t_n \rightarrow s$.
 (h) Prove that $\inf\{1/n : n \in \mathbb{N}\} = 0$.

Proof.

- (a) Since
- $1 - 1/n < 1$
- for all
- n
- , the number 1 is an upper bound of
- S
- . Let
- $\varepsilon > 0$
- . Choose
- $n > 1/\varepsilon$
- . Then

$$1 - \frac{1}{n} > 1 - \varepsilon.$$

Hence, for every $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $s \in S$ with $s > 1 - \varepsilon$. By the ε -characterization of the supremum,

$$\sup S = 1.$$

- (b) Suppose
- $na \leq b$
- for every
- $n \in \mathbb{N}$
- . Then

$$E = \{na : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$$

is nonempty and bounded above, so $s_0 = \sup E$ exists. Since $a > 0$, the number $s_0 - a$ is strictly smaller than s_0 , hence it is not an upper bound of E . Thus there is $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$s_0 - a < n_0 a.$$

Therefore

$$s_0 < (n_0 + 1)a \in E,$$

a contradiction. Hence $na > b$ for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

- (c) Since
- $\beta - \alpha > 0$
- , the Archimedean property gives
- $n \in \mathbb{N}$
- with

$$n(\beta - \alpha) > 1.$$

Then $n\beta - n\alpha > 1$, so there is an integer m such that

$$n\alpha < m < n\beta.$$

Let $q = m/n$. Then $q \in \mathbb{Q}$ and

$$\alpha < q < \beta.$$

- (d) Choose
- $n \in \mathbb{N}$
- so large that

$$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{n} < \beta - \alpha.$$

By part (c), choose $q \in \mathbb{Q}$ such that

$$\alpha - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{n} < q < \beta - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{n}.$$

Let

$$x = q + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{n}.$$

Then $\alpha < x < \beta$. Also $\sqrt{2}/n$ is irrational, so x is irrational.

- (e) Let
- $a \in A$
- and
- $b \in B$
- . Then

$$a + b \leq \sup A + \sup B.$$

So $\sup A + \sup B$ is an upper bound of $A + B$, and therefore

$$\sup(A + B) \leq \sup A + \sup B.$$

Let $\varepsilon > 0$. Choose $a \in A$ and $b \in B$ such that

$$\sup A - \frac{\varepsilon}{2} < a \leq \sup A, \quad \sup B - \frac{\varepsilon}{2} < b \leq \sup B.$$

Then

$$a + b > \sup A + \sup B - \varepsilon.$$

Hence

$$\sup(A + B) \geq \sup A + \sup B - \varepsilon.$$

Since $\varepsilon > 0$ is arbitrary,

$$\sup(A + B) = \sup A + \sup B.$$

For the infimum, apply part (a) to $-A$ and $-B$:

$$\begin{aligned} \inf(A + B) &= -\sup(-(A + B)) = -\sup((-A) + (-B)) \\ &= -\sup(-A) - \sup(-B) = \inf A + \inf B. \end{aligned}$$

- (f) For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, the number $s - 1/n$ is not an upper bound of T . Choose $x_n \in T$ such that

$$s - \frac{1}{n} < x_n \leq s.$$

Then

$$0 \leq s - x_n < \frac{1}{n},$$

so $x_n \rightarrow s$.

- (g) Choose (x_n) as in part (f) and define

$$t_n = \max\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}.$$

Then $t_n \in T$, (t_n) is increasing, and

$$s - \frac{1}{n} < x_n \leq t_n \leq s.$$

Hence

$$0 \leq s - t_n < \frac{1}{n},$$

so $t_n \rightarrow s$.

- (h) Since $1/n > 0$ for all n , the number 0 is a lower bound. Let $\varepsilon > 0$. Choose $n > 1/\varepsilon$. Then

$$\frac{1}{n} < \varepsilon.$$

So no positive number can be a lower bound. Therefore

$$\inf \left\{ \frac{1}{n} : n \in \mathbb{N} \right\} = 0.$$

Exam Problem 3

- (a) Prove directly that $(-1)^n/n \rightarrow 0$.
 (b) Prove directly that $(n^3 + 2)/(n^2 + 1) \rightarrow +\infty$.
 (c) Prove that $\sin n/n \rightarrow 0$.
 (d) If $a_n \rightarrow 0$ and (b_n) is bounded, prove that $a_n b_n \rightarrow 0$.
 (e) If $a_n \rightarrow +\infty$ and $b_n \geq c > 0$ eventually, prove that $a_n b_n \rightarrow +\infty$.
 (f) For positive a_n , prove that $a_n \rightarrow +\infty$ iff $1/a_n \rightarrow 0$.

Proof.

- (a) Let $\varepsilon > 0$. Choose $N > 1/\varepsilon$. Then for $n > N$,

$$\left| \frac{(-1)^n}{n} \right| = \frac{1}{n} < \varepsilon.$$

Hence $(-1)^n/n \rightarrow 0$.

- (b) Let $M > 0$. Choose $N = 2M$. If $n > N$, then $n \geq 1$ and so $n^2 + 1 \leq 2n^2$. Therefore

$$\frac{n^3 + 2}{n^2 + 1} \geq \frac{n^3}{2n^2} \geq \frac{n^3}{2n^2} = \frac{n}{2} > \frac{N}{2} = M.$$

Hence $(n^3 + 2)/(n^2 + 1) \rightarrow +\infty$.

- (c) Since $-1 \leq \sin n \leq 1$, we have

$$-\frac{1}{n} \leq \frac{\sin n}{n} \leq \frac{1}{n}.$$

The outer sequences converge to 0. By the squeeze theorem,

$$\frac{\sin n}{n} \rightarrow 0.$$

- (d) Choose $M > 0$ such that $|b_n| \leq M$ for all n . Let $\varepsilon > 0$. Since $a_n \rightarrow 0$, there is N such that

$$|a_n| < \frac{\varepsilon}{M}$$

for $n > N$. Then for $n > N$,

$$|a_n b_n| \leq M |a_n| < \varepsilon.$$

Thus $a_n b_n \rightarrow 0$.

- (e) Let $M > 0$. Since $a_n \rightarrow +\infty$, there exists $N \geq N_0$ such that

$$a_n > \frac{M}{c}$$

for all $n > N$. Then for $n > N$,

$$a_n b_n \geq c a_n > M.$$

Hence $a_n b_n \rightarrow +\infty$.

- (f) Assume first that $a_n \rightarrow +\infty$. Let $\varepsilon > 0$. Put $M = 1/\varepsilon$. Then $a_n > M$ eventually, hence

$$\frac{1}{a_n} < \varepsilon$$

eventually. So $1/a_n \rightarrow 0$.

Conversely, assume $1/a_n \rightarrow 0$. Let $M > 0$. Put $\varepsilon = 1/M$. Then

$$\frac{1}{a_n} < \frac{1}{M}$$

eventually. Since $a_n > 0$, this is equivalent to $a_n > M$ eventually. Thus $a_n \rightarrow +\infty$.

Exam Problem 4

Let

$$x_1 = 1, \quad x_{n+1} = \sqrt{2 + x_n}.$$

- (a) Prove that $x_n \leq 2$ for all n .
 (b) Prove that (x_n) is increasing.
 (c) Deduce that (x_n) converges and find its limit.
 (d) If $|s_{n+1} - s_n| < 2^{-n}$ for all n , prove that (s_n) is Cauchy and convergent.
 (e) Show that the conclusion in (d) fails if one only assumes $|s_{n+1} - s_n| < 1/n$.
 (f) If (s_n) is Cauchy and a subsequence (s_{n_k}) converges to L , prove that $s_n \rightarrow L$.
 (g) If $a_n \in \mathbb{Z}$ for all n and (a_n) converges, prove that (a_n) is eventually constant.
 (h) Let (u_n) be monotone. Prove that (u_n) converges iff (u_n^2) converges. Give a non-monotone counterexample.
 (i) Let

$$s_1 = 5, \quad s_{n+1} = \frac{s_n^2 + 5}{2s_n}.$$

Prove that (s_n) converges and compute its limit.

Proof.

- (a) For $n = 1$, $x_1 = 1 \leq 2$. Assume $x_n \leq 2$. Then

$$x_{n+1} = \sqrt{2 + x_n} \leq \sqrt{4} = 2.$$

Hence $x_n \leq 2$ for all n .

- (b) Since $0 < x_n \leq 2$, we have

$$(x_n - 2)(x_n + 1) \leq 0.$$

Therefore

$$x_n^2 \leq x_n + 2.$$

Since both sides are nonnegative,

$$x_n \leq \sqrt{x_n + 2} = x_{n+1}.$$

So (x_n) is increasing.

- (c) By parts (a) and (b), (x_n) is increasing and bounded above. Hence it converges. Let $x_n \rightarrow L$. Then

$$L = \sqrt{2 + L}.$$

So

$$L^2 - L - 2 = 0, \quad (L - 2)(L + 1) = 0.$$

Since $L > 0$, we get $L = 2$.

- (d) Let $m > n$. Then

$$|s_m - s_n| \leq \sum_{k=n}^{m-1} |s_{k+1} - s_k| < \sum_{k=n}^{m-1} 2^{-k} < \sum_{k=n}^{\infty} 2^{-k} = 2^{-n+1}.$$

Given $\varepsilon > 0$, choose N so that $2^{-N+1} < \varepsilon$. Then for $m > n \geq N$,

$$|s_m - s_n| < \varepsilon.$$

Hence (s_n) is Cauchy, and therefore convergent.

- (e) Let

$$s_n = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \cdots + \frac{1}{n}.$$

Then

$$|s_{n+1} - s_n| = \frac{1}{n+1} < \frac{1}{n}.$$

But

$$s_{2n} - s_n = \frac{1}{n+1} + \cdots + \frac{1}{2n} \geq n \cdot \frac{1}{2n} = \frac{1}{2}.$$

So (s_n) is not Cauchy. Hence the conclusion fails.

- (f) Let $\varepsilon > 0$. Since (s_n) is Cauchy, choose N_1 such that

$$|s_n - s_m| < \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$$

for all $m, n \geq N_1$. Since $s_{n_k} \rightarrow L$, choose K so that $n_K \geq N_1$ and

$$|s_{n_K} - L| < \frac{\varepsilon}{2}.$$

Then for $n \geq n_K$,

$$|s_n - L| \leq |s_n - s_{n_K}| + |s_{n_K} - L| < \varepsilon.$$

Hence $s_n \rightarrow L$.

- (g) Let $a_n \rightarrow L$. Choose N so that

$$|a_n - L| < \frac{1}{2}$$

for all $n \geq N$. The interval $(L - 1/2, L + 1/2)$ contains at most one integer. Since each $a_n \in \mathbb{Z}$, all a_n with $n \geq N$ must be equal to that integer. Thus (a_n) is eventually constant.

- (h) If $u_n \rightarrow L$, then by the limit laws,

$$u_n^2 \rightarrow L^2.$$

Conversely, if (u_n^2) converges, then it is bounded, so $|u_n|$ is bounded. Hence (u_n) is bounded. Since (u_n) is monotone, it converges. A non-monotone counterexample is

$$v_n = (-1)^n.$$

Then $v_n^2 = 1$ for all n , so (v_n^2) converges, but (v_n) does not.

- (i) First,

$$s_{n+1} - \sqrt{5} = \frac{s_n^2 + 5 - 2\sqrt{5}s_n}{2s_n} = \frac{(s_n - \sqrt{5})^2}{2s_n} \geq 0.$$

Since $s_1 = 5 > \sqrt{5}$, induction gives

$$s_n \geq \sqrt{5}$$

for all n . Also,

$$s_{n+1} - s_n = \frac{s_n^2 + 5}{2s_n} - s_n = \frac{5 - s_n^2}{2s_n} \leq 0,$$

because $s_n \geq \sqrt{5}$. Thus (s_n) is decreasing and bounded below by $\sqrt{5}$, so it converges. Let $s_n \rightarrow L$. Since $L > 0$,

$$L = \frac{L^2 + 5}{2L}.$$

Hence $L^2 = 5$, and therefore $L = \sqrt{5}$.

Exam Problem 5 Problem 5A.

- (a) Let $u_n = (-1)^n + 1/n$. Find $\limsup u_n$ and $\liminf u_n$.
 (b) Show that (u_n) does not converge.
 (c) Use Bolzano–Weierstrass to prove that $(\sin n)$ has a convergent subsequence.
 (d) Let (v_n) be bounded. Assume every convergent subsequence of (v_n) has the same limit L . Prove that $v_n \rightarrow L$.
 (e) Let $x_n = (-1)^n(1 + 1/n)$. Find all subsequential limits.
 (f) Using the definition of limit, prove that $((-1)^n)$ does not converge.
 (g) Let (r_n) be an enumeration of \mathbb{Q} . Prove that there exists a subsequence (r_{n_k}) such that $r_{n_k} \rightarrow +\infty$.
 (h) Prove that $\liminf s_n = -\limsup(-s_n)$.
 (i) If $\sigma_n = (s_1 + \cdots + s_n)/n$ and $s_n \rightarrow s$, prove that $\sigma_n \rightarrow s$.
 (j) Give an example where (σ_n) converges but (s_n) does not.

Proof.

- (a) For even indices,

$$u_{2k} = 1 + \frac{1}{2k} \rightarrow 1.$$

For odd indices,

$$u_{2k+1} = -1 + \frac{1}{2k+1} \rightarrow -1.$$

Hence

$$\limsup u_n = 1, \quad \liminf u_n = -1.$$

- (b) The even subsequence converges to 1 and the odd subsequence converges to -1 . Since the two limits are different, (u_n) does not converge.
 (c) The sequence $(\sin n)$ is bounded because

$$-1 \leq \sin n \leq 1$$

for all n . By Bolzano–Weierstrass, it has a convergent subsequence.

- (d) Suppose $v_n \not\rightarrow L$. Then there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that for every N there is $n \geq N$ with

$$|v_n - L| \geq \varepsilon.$$

Choose a subsequence (v_{n_k}) satisfying

$$|v_{n_k} - L| \geq \varepsilon$$

for all k . Since (v_n) is bounded, Bolzano–Weierstrass gives a convergent subsequence $(v_{n_{k_j}})$. Its limit must be L by hypothesis, but every term stays at least ε away from L , which is impossible. Hence $v_n \rightarrow L$.

- (e) For even indices,

$$x_{2k} = 1 + \frac{1}{2k} \rightarrow 1.$$

For odd indices,

$$x_{2k+1} = -1 - \frac{1}{2k+1} \rightarrow -1.$$

Thus 1 and -1 are subsequential limits. Every subsequence has a further even or odd subsequence, so there are no others. Therefore the set of subsequential limits is $\{-1, 1\}$.

(f) Suppose $(-1)^n \rightarrow L$. Take $\varepsilon = 1$. Then there is N such that

$$|(-1)^n - L| < 1$$

for all $n > N$. Choose an even $n > N$ and an odd $m > N$. Then

$$|1 - L| < 1, \quad |-1 - L| < 1.$$

By the triangle inequality,

$$2 = |1 - (-1)| \leq |1 - L| + |L + 1| < 2,$$

a contradiction. Hence $(-1)^n$ does not converge.

(g) Choose n_1 so that $r_{n_1} > 1$. Suppose $n_1 < \dots < n_k$ are chosen with

$$r_{n_j} > j$$

for $j = 1, \dots, k$. The finite set $\{r_1, \dots, r_{n_k}\}$ contains only finitely many integers, so choose an integer $m > k + 1$ that is not in it. Since (r_n) enumerates \mathbb{Q} , there exists $n_{k+1} > n_k$ such that

$$r_{n_{k+1}} = m.$$

Then $r_{n_{k+1}} > k + 1$. Hence $r_{n_k} > k$ for every k , so $r_{n_k} \rightarrow +\infty$.

(h) For each N ,

$$\sup\{-s_n : n > N\} = -\inf\{s_n : n > N\}.$$

Taking limits as $N \rightarrow \infty$ gives

$$\limsup(-s_n) = -\liminf s_n.$$

Thus

$$\liminf s_n = -\limsup(-s_n).$$

(i) Write

$$\sigma_n - s = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n (s_k - s).$$

Let $\varepsilon > 0$. Choose N so that

$$|s_k - s| < \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$$

for all $k \geq N$. Set

$$A = |s_1 - s| + \dots + |s_{N-1} - s|.$$

Choose $M \geq N$ so large that $A/M < \varepsilon/2$. Then for $n \geq M$,

$$|\sigma_n - s| \leq \frac{A}{n} + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=N}^n |s_k - s| < \frac{\varepsilon}{2} + \frac{n - N + 1}{n} \cdot \frac{\varepsilon}{2} < \varepsilon.$$

Hence $\sigma_n \rightarrow s$.

(j) Take

$$s_n = (-1)^n.$$

Then (s_n) does not converge. But

$$\sigma_{2m} = 0, \quad \sigma_{2m+1} = -\frac{1}{2m+1},$$

so $\sigma_n \rightarrow 0$.

Problem 5B.

(a) Let (n_k) be strictly increasing in \mathbb{N} . Prove that $n_k \geq k$ for all k .

(b) Determine whether the statement is true or false: if $(|a_n|)$ converges, then (a_n) converges.

(c) If $a_n \rightarrow a$ and $b_n \rightarrow b$, prove from the definition that $a_n + b_n \rightarrow a + b$.

(d) If $a_n \leq b_n$ for all n , and $a_n \rightarrow a$, $b_n \rightarrow b$, prove that $a \leq b$.

(e) If $a_n \geq 0$ for all n and $a_n \rightarrow a > 0$, prove that $\sqrt{a_n} \rightarrow \sqrt{a}$.

(f) Let $S, T \subset \mathbb{R}$ be nonempty and bounded. Prove that

$$\sup S \leq \inf T \quad \text{iff} \quad s \leq t \text{ for all } s \in S, t \in T.$$

(g) If $F = \{a_1, \dots, a_N\} \subset \mathbb{R}$ is finite, prove that every sequence in F has a convergent subsequence whose limit lies in F .

(h) Prove the squeeze theorem for sequences.

(i) If $a_n \rightarrow a$ and $b_n \rightarrow b$, prove from the definition that $a_n b_n \rightarrow ab$.

Proof.

(a) We use induction. Since $n_1 \in \mathbb{N}$, we have $n_1 \geq 1$. Assume $n_k \geq k$. Since (n_k) is strictly increasing,

$$n_{k+1} > n_k \geq k.$$

Because n_{k+1} is an integer, $n_{k+1} \geq k + 1$. Thus $n_k \geq k$ for all k .

(b) False. Take $a_n = (-1)^n$. Then $|a_n| = 1$ for all n , so $(|a_n|)$ converges, but (a_n) does not.

(c) Let $\varepsilon > 0$. Since $a_n \rightarrow a$, there is N_1 such that

$$|a_n - a| < \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$$

for $n \geq N_1$. Since $b_n \rightarrow b$, there is N_2 such that

$$|b_n - b| < \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$$

for $n \geq N_2$. If $n \geq N = \max\{N_1, N_2\}$, then

$$|(a_n + b_n) - (a + b)| \leq |a_n - a| + |b_n - b| < \varepsilon.$$

Hence $a_n + b_n \rightarrow a + b$.

(d) Suppose $a > b$. Let

$$\varepsilon = \frac{a - b}{2} > 0.$$

Choose N_1 so that $|a_n - a| < \varepsilon$ for $n \geq N_1$, and N_2 so that $|b_n - b| < \varepsilon$ for $n \geq N_2$. Then for $n \geq N = \max\{N_1, N_2\}$,

$$a_n > a - \varepsilon = \frac{a + b}{2}, \quad b_n < b + \varepsilon = \frac{a + b}{2},$$

which contradicts $a_n \leq b_n$. Hence $a \leq b$.

(e) Let $\varepsilon > 0$. Since $a_n \rightarrow a$, there is N such that

$$|a_n - a| < \varepsilon\sqrt{a}$$

for all $n \geq N$. Then

$$|\sqrt{a_n} - \sqrt{a}| = \frac{|a_n - a|}{\sqrt{a_n} + \sqrt{a}} \leq \frac{|a_n - a|}{\sqrt{a}} < \varepsilon.$$

Hence $\sqrt{a_n} \rightarrow \sqrt{a}$.

(f) Suppose first that $\sup S \leq \inf T$. Since $\sup S$ is an upper bound of S and $\inf T$ is a lower bound of T ,

$$s \leq \sup S \leq \inf T \leq t$$

for every $s \in S$ and $t \in T$. Hence $s \leq t$ for all $s \in S, t \in T$.

Conversely, suppose $s \leq t$ for all $s \in S$ and $t \in T$. Fix $t \in T$. Then t is an upper bound of S , so

$$\sup S \leq t.$$

Since this holds for every $t \in T$, the number $\sup S$ is a lower bound of T . Therefore

$$\sup S \leq \inf T.$$

(g) Since F is finite, some value $a_j \in F$ occurs infinitely often in the sequence. Choosing those terms gives a constant subsequence, hence a convergent subsequence whose limit is $a_j \in F$.

(h) Let $\varepsilon > 0$. Since $a_n \rightarrow L$, there is N_1 such that

$$|a_n - L| < \varepsilon$$

for $n \geq N_1$, hence $a_n > L - \varepsilon$. Since $c_n \rightarrow L$, there is N_2 such that

$$|c_n - L| < \varepsilon$$

for $n \geq N_2$, hence $c_n < L + \varepsilon$. If $n \geq N = \max\{N_1, N_2\}$, then

$$L - \varepsilon < a_n \leq b_n \leq c_n < L + \varepsilon.$$

Therefore $|b_n - L| < \varepsilon$, so $b_n \rightarrow L$.

- (i) Let $\varepsilon > 0$. Since $a_n \rightarrow a$, choose N_1 such that

$$|a_n - a| < \varepsilon$$

for $n \geq N_1$. Then $|a_n| \leq |a| + 1$ for $n \geq N_1$. Choose N_2 such that

$$|b_n - b| < \frac{\varepsilon}{2(|a| + 1)}$$

for $n \geq N_2$, and choose N_3 such that

$$|a_n - a| < \frac{\varepsilon}{2(|b| + 1)}$$

for $n \geq N_3$. Then for $n \geq N = \max\{N_1, N_2, N_3\}$,

$$|a_n b_n - ab| = |a_n(b_n - b) + b(a_n - a)| \leq |a_n||b_n - b| + |b||a_n - a| < \varepsilon.$$

Hence $a_n b_n \rightarrow ab$.

Problem 5C.

- (a) Suppose $a_n \rightarrow a$. Prove that (a_n) is bounded.
 (b) Suppose $a_n \rightarrow a$ and $a_n \rightarrow b$. Prove that $a = b$.
 (c) Suppose $a_n \rightarrow a$ and (a_{n_k}) is a subsequence. Prove that $a_{n_k} \rightarrow a$.
 (d) Prove that every sequence of real numbers has a monotone subsequence.
 (e) Let (a_n) be bounded and let $L = \limsup a_n$. Prove that there exists a subsequence (a_{n_k}) such that $a_{n_k} \rightarrow L$.

Proof.

- (a) Since $a_n \rightarrow a$, there is N such that

$$|a_n - a| < 1$$

for $n \geq N$. Then $|a_n| \leq |a| + 1$ for $n \geq N$. Let

$$M = \max\{|a_1|, \dots, |a_{N-1}|, |a| + 1\}.$$

Then $|a_n| \leq M$ for all n .

- (b) Let $\varepsilon > 0$. Choose N_1 so that $|a_n - a| < \varepsilon/2$ for $n \geq N_1$, and N_2 so that $|a_n - b| < \varepsilon/2$ for $n \geq N_2$. Then for $n \geq N = \max\{N_1, N_2\}$,

$$|a - b| \leq |a - a_n| + |a_n - b| < \varepsilon.$$

Since $\varepsilon > 0$ is arbitrary, $a = b$.

- (c) Let $\varepsilon > 0$. Since $a_n \rightarrow a$, choose N such that

$$|a_n - a| < \varepsilon$$

for all $n \geq N$. Since $n_k \geq k$, there exists K with $n_K \geq N$. Then for $k \geq K$,

$$|a_{n_k} - a| < \varepsilon.$$

Hence $a_{n_k} \rightarrow a$.

- (d) If a sequence is increasing, then it is itself a monotone subsequence. Otherwise, call s_n dominant if $s_n > s_m$ for all $m > n$. If there are infinitely many dominant terms, choose them in order. The resulting subsequence is decreasing. If there are only finitely many dominant terms, choose an index after the last dominant term. Since that term is not dominant, choose a later term at least as large. Repeating inductively gives an increasing subsequence. Therefore every sequence has a monotone subsequence.
 (e) For each $k \in \mathbb{N}$, choose N_k so large that

$$\sup\{a_n : n > N_k\} < L + \frac{1}{k}.$$

Since $L = \limsup a_n$, there must exist $n_k > \max\{N_k, n_{k-1}\}$ such that

$$a_{n_k} > L - \frac{1}{k}.$$

Otherwise, all $n > N_k$ would satisfy $a_n \leq L - 1/k$, forcing the

tail supremum to be at most $L - 1/k$. Thus

$$L - \frac{1}{k} < a_{n_k} < L + \frac{1}{k}.$$

Hence $a_{n_k} \rightarrow L$.

Exam Problem 6

- (a) Prove that if $\sum a_n$ converges, then $a_n \rightarrow 0$.
 (b) Compute $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 1/(n(n+1))$.
 (c) Construct (a_n) with $a_n \rightarrow 0$ but $\sum a_n$ diverges.
 (d) Show that $\sum_{n=1}^N (\sqrt{n+1} - \sqrt{n}) = \sqrt{N+1} - 1$.
 (e) If $\sum |a_n|$ converges and (b_n) is bounded, prove that $\sum a_n b_n$ converges.
 (f) Construct a divergent series $\sum a_n$ such that $\sum a_n^2$ converges.
 (g) Construct a convergent series $\sum a_n$ such that $\sum a_n^2$ diverges.

Proof.

- (a) Let $s_n = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k$. If $\sum a_n$ converges, then $s_n \rightarrow s$ for some $s \in \mathbb{R}$. But

$$a_n = s_n - s_{n-1}.$$

Hence

$$a_n \rightarrow s - s = 0.$$

- (b) Since

$$\frac{1}{n(n+1)} = \frac{1}{n} - \frac{1}{n+1},$$

we have

$$\sum_{n=1}^N \frac{1}{n(n+1)} = \sum_{n=1}^N \left(\frac{1}{n} - \frac{1}{n+1} \right) = 1 - \frac{1}{N+1}.$$

Letting $N \rightarrow \infty$ gives

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n(n+1)} = 1.$$

- (c) Take $a_n = 1/n$. Then $a_n \rightarrow 0$, but the harmonic series diverges.
 (d) The sum telescopes:

$$(\sqrt{2} - 1) + (\sqrt{3} - \sqrt{2}) + \dots + (\sqrt{N+1} - \sqrt{N}) = \sqrt{N+1} - 1.$$

- (e) Choose $M > 0$ with $|b_n| \leq M$ for all n . Then

$$|a_n b_n| \leq M|a_n|.$$

Since $\sum |a_n|$ converges, the comparison test gives convergence of $\sum |a_n b_n|$. Hence $\sum a_n b_n$ converges absolutely.

- (f) Take $a_n = 1/n$. Then $\sum a_n$ diverges, while $\sum a_n^2 = \sum 1/n^2$ converges.
 (g) Take $a_n = (-1)^{n+1}/\sqrt{n}$. Then $\sum a_n$ converges by the alternating-series test, but $\sum a_n^2 = \sum 1/n$ diverges.

Exam Problem 7

Determine whether each series converges or diverges:

(a) $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{n}{n^3 + 1}$

(b) $\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n \log n}$

(c) $\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n(\log n)^2}$

(d) $\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n(\log n)^3}$

- (e) If (a_n) is decreasing and positive and $\sum a_n$ converges, prove that $na_n \rightarrow 0$.

Proof.(a) For $n \geq 1$,

$$0 \leq \frac{n}{n^3+1} \leq \frac{n}{n^3} = \frac{1}{n^2}.$$

Since $\sum 1/n^2$ converges, the comparison test yields convergence.(b) Let $f(x) = 1/(x \log x)$ for $x \geq 2$. Then f is positive and decreasing, and

$$\int_2^N \frac{dx}{x \log x} = \log \log N - \log \log 2 \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Hence the series diverges by the integral test.

(c) Let $f(x) = 1/(x(\log x)^2)$ for $x \geq 2$. Then

$$\int_2^\infty \frac{dx}{x(\log x)^2} = \int_{\log 2}^\infty \frac{du}{u^2} = \frac{1}{\log 2} < \infty.$$

Hence the series converges by the integral test.

(d) Let $f(x) = 1/(x(\log x)^3)$ for $x \geq 2$. Then

$$\int_2^\infty \frac{dx}{x(\log x)^3} = \int_{\log 2}^\infty \frac{du}{u^3} < \infty.$$

Hence the series converges by the integral test.

(e) For $n \geq 2$, each index

$$k = \left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor + 1, \dots, n$$

satisfies $a_k \geq a_n$. There are at least $n/2$ such terms. Thus

$$\frac{n}{2} a_n \leq \sum_{k=\lfloor n/2 \rfloor + 1}^n a_k.$$

The right-hand side is a tail of a convergent series, so it tends to 0. Therefore $na_n \rightarrow 0$.**Exam Problem 8**

Determine whether each series converges or diverges, and state whether the convergence is absolute or conditional:

(a)
$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(n!)^2}{(2n)!}$$

(b)
$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+1} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$$

(c)
$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{n}{n+1} \right)^{n^2}$$

(d)
$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1 + (-1)^n/2}{2^n}$$

Proof.(a) Let $a_n = (n!)^2/(2n)!$. Then

$$\frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} = \frac{(n+1)^2}{(2n+2)(2n+1)} = \frac{n+1}{2(2n+1)} \rightarrow \frac{1}{4} < 1.$$

Hence the series converges by the ratio test. Since the terms are nonnegative, the convergence is absolute.

(b) Let $b_n = 1/\sqrt{n}$. Then $b_n \downarrow 0$, so

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+1} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$$

converges by the alternating-series test. But

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$$

diverges. Hence the convergence is conditional.

(c) Let $a_n = (n/(n+1))^{n^2}$. Then

$$\sqrt[n]{a_n} = \left(\frac{n}{n+1} \right)^n = \left(1 + \frac{1}{n} \right)^{-n} \rightarrow e^{-1} < 1.$$

So the series converges absolutely by the root test.

(d) Since

$$0 \leq 1 + \frac{(-1)^n}{2} \leq \frac{3}{2},$$

we have

$$0 \leq \frac{1 + (-1)^n/2}{2^n} \leq \frac{3}{2^{n+1}}.$$

The comparison geometric series converges, so the given series converges. In particular it converges absolutely.

Exam Problem 9(a) Prove that $|x|$ is continuous on \mathbb{R} .(b) Define $g(x) = \sin(1/x)$ for $x \neq 0$ and $g(0) = 0$. Prove that g is not continuous at 0.(c) Let $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be continuous and assume $f(x) \neq 0$ on $[a, b]$. Prove that there exists $m > 0$ such that $|f(x)| \geq m$ for all $x \in [a, b]$.

(d) Use IVT to prove that every real polynomial of odd degree has a real root.

(e) Define $F(x) = \sin(1/x^2)$ for $x \neq 0$ and $F(0) = 0$. Find sequences $a_n, b_n \rightarrow 0$ with $F(a_n) = 1$ and $F(b_n) = -1$.(f) Define $h(x) = x$ for $x \in \mathbb{Q}$ and $h(x) = 0$ for $x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Q}$. Determine all continuity points of h .(g) Let $f: [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be continuous, $f(0) > 0$, and $f(1) = 0$. Prove that there exists $x_0 \in (0, 1]$ such that $f(x_0) = 0$ and $f(x) > 0$ for all $x \in [0, x_0)$.(h) Let $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be continuous and let $x_1, \dots, x_n \in [a, b]$. Prove that there exists $z \in [a, b]$ such that

$$f(z) = \frac{f(x_1) + \dots + f(x_n)}{n}.$$

Proof.(a) Let $x_n \rightarrow x_0$. Then

$$||x_n| - |x_0|| \leq |x_n - x_0| \rightarrow 0.$$

Hence $|x_n| \rightarrow |x_0|$. Therefore $|x|$ is continuous on \mathbb{R} .

(b) Let

$$x_n = \frac{1}{\pi/2 + 2\pi n}, \quad y_n = \frac{1}{3\pi/2 + 2\pi n}.$$

Then $x_n \rightarrow 0$ and $y_n \rightarrow 0$. Also

$$g(x_n) = \sin\left(\frac{1}{x_n}\right) = 1, \quad g(y_n) = \sin\left(\frac{1}{y_n}\right) = -1.$$

The image limits disagree, so g is not continuous at 0.(c) Since f is continuous, so is $|f|$. By the Extreme Value Theorem, $|f|$ attains a minimum on $[a, b]$; say

$$|f(x_0)| \leq |f(x)|$$

for all $x \in [a, b]$. Put $m = |f(x_0)|$. Since $f(x) \neq 0$ for all x , we have $m > 0$. Hence

$$|f(x)| \geq m > 0$$

for all $x \in [a, b]$.(d) Let p be a polynomial of odd degree. For large K , the highest-degree term dominates, so $p(-K)$ and $p(K)$ have opposite signs. Since polynomials are continuous, the Intermediate Value Theorem gives $c \in [-K, K]$ such that

$$p(c) = 0.$$

(e) Let

$$a_n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi/2 + 2\pi n}}, \quad b_n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3\pi/2 + 2\pi n}}.$$

Then $a_n \rightarrow 0$ and $b_n \rightarrow 0$. Also

$$F(a_n) = \sin\left(\frac{1}{a_n^2}\right) = 1, \quad F(b_n) = \sin\left(\frac{1}{b_n^2}\right) = -1.$$

Hence F is not continuous at 0.

- (f) The only continuity point is 0. If $a \neq 0$, choose rationals $r_n \rightarrow a$ and irrationals $t_n \rightarrow a$. Then

$$h(r_n) = r_n \rightarrow a, \quad h(t_n) = 0 \rightarrow 0.$$

Since $a \neq 0$, the image limits differ, so h is not continuous at a . At 0, we have $|h(x)| \leq |x|$. Therefore if $x_n \rightarrow 0$, then $h(x_n) \rightarrow 0 = h(0)$. So h is continuous at 0.

- (g) Let

$$Z = \{x \in (0, 1] : f(x) = 0\}, \quad x_0 = \inf Z.$$

Since $1 \in Z$, the set Z is nonempty. Choose $z_n \in Z$ with

$$x_0 \leq z_n < x_0 + \frac{1}{n}.$$

Then $z_n \rightarrow x_0$. Since $f(z_n) = 0$ for all n and f is continuous,

$$f(x_0) = 0.$$

Thus $x_0 \in Z$. If there were $y < x_0$ with $f(y) \leq 0$, then $f(0) > 0$ and the Intermediate Value Theorem would give a zero in $[0, y]$, contradicting the minimality of x_0 . Hence

$$f(x) > 0$$

for all $x \in [0, x_0)$.

- (h) Let

$$A = \frac{f(x_1) + \cdots + f(x_n)}{n}, \quad m = \min_j f(x_j), \quad M = \max_j f(x_j).$$

Then $m \leq A \leq M$. Choose indices p, q with $f(x_p) = m$ and $f(x_q) = M$. Since A lies between $f(x_p)$ and $f(x_q)$, the Intermediate Value Theorem gives z between x_p and x_q such that

$$f(z) = A.$$

- (b) We first show that if $x < y < z$, then $f(y)$ lies between $f(x)$ and $f(z)$. If not, then either $f(y) > \max\{f(x), f(z)\}$ or $f(y) < \min\{f(x), f(z)\}$. In either case, the Intermediate Value Theorem produces two different points with the same f -value, contradicting injectivity. Hence f cannot turn around, so it is monotone. Since it is one-to-one, the monotonicity is strict. Now $[a, b]$ is an interval, so $f([a, b])$ is an interval. By the inverse continuity theorem for intervals, the inverse of a continuous strictly monotone function is continuous. Therefore

$$f^{-1} : f([a, b]) \rightarrow [a, b]$$

is continuous.

- (c) Let

$$x_n = \frac{1}{n}, \quad y_n = \frac{1}{n+1}.$$

Then $|x_n - y_n| \rightarrow 0$, but

$$\left| \frac{1}{x_n} - \frac{1}{y_n} \right| = |n - (n+1)| = 1$$

for every n . Hence $1/x$ is not uniformly continuous on $(0, 1]$.

- (d) Let $\varepsilon > 0$. By uniform continuity, choose $\delta > 0$ such that

$$|x - y| < \delta \implies |f(x) - f(y)| < \varepsilon$$

for all $x, y \in E$. Since (x_n) is Cauchy, there is N such that

$$|x_n - x_m| < \delta$$

for all $m, n \geq N$. Then

$$|f(x_n) - f(x_m)| < \varepsilon$$

for all $m, n \geq N$. Hence $(f(x_n))$ is Cauchy.

- (e) For each $x \in [0, 1]$, choose a sequence $x_n \in E$ with $x_n \rightarrow x$. Then (x_n) is Cauchy, so by part (d), $(f(x_n))$ is Cauchy, hence convergent. If (y_n) is another sequence in E with $y_n \rightarrow x$, interleave the two sequences. The interleaved sequence is Cauchy, so its image is Cauchy. Therefore the two image subsequences have the same limit. This shows that the value

$$F(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n)$$

is well defined. If $x \in E$, choose the constant sequence $x_n = x$. Then $F(x) = f(x)$, so F extends f . To prove continuity, let $\varepsilon > 0$ and choose $\delta > 0$ from the uniform continuity of f on E . If $x, y \in [0, 1]$ and $|x - y| < \delta/3$, choose sequences $x_n, y_n \in E$ with $x_n \rightarrow x$ and $y_n \rightarrow y$. For large n ,

$$|x_n - x| < \frac{\delta}{3}, \quad |y_n - y| < \frac{\delta}{3},$$

so

$$|x_n - y_n| < \delta.$$

Hence

$$|f(x_n) - f(y_n)| < \varepsilon.$$

Letting $n \rightarrow \infty$ gives

$$|F(x) - F(y)| \leq \varepsilon.$$

Thus F is uniformly continuous, hence continuous, on $[0, 1]$. Uniqueness is immediate from continuity and density of E .

- (f) Let $x \neq y$. By the Mean Value Theorem, there exists c between x and y such that

$$\frac{f(x) - f(y)}{x - y} = f'(c).$$

Hence

$$|f(x) - f(y)| = |f'(c)| |x - y| \leq M|x - y|.$$

The case $x = y$ is trivial.

- (g) Since $f(\mathbb{R})$ is bounded, there exists $M > 0$ such that $|f(x)| \leq M$ for all x . Let

$$g(x) = f(x) - x.$$

Exam Problem 10

- (a) Let $f : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be continuous. Prove that f has a fixed point.
- (b) Suppose $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuous and one-to-one. Prove that f is strictly monotone and that $f^{-1} : f([a, b]) \rightarrow [a, b]$ is continuous.
- (c) Prove that $1/x$ is not uniformly continuous on $(0, 1]$.
- (d) If $f : E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is uniformly continuous and (x_n) is a Cauchy sequence in E , prove that $(f(x_n))$ is Cauchy.
- (e) Let $E = (0, 1) \cap \mathbb{Q}$, and let $f : E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be uniformly continuous. Show that f extends uniquely to a continuous function on $[0, 1]$.
- (f) Suppose $|f'(x)| \leq M$ on $[a, b]$. Prove that $|f(x) - f(y)| \leq M|x - y|$ for all $x, y \in [a, b]$.
- (g) Suppose $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuous and $f(\mathbb{R})$ is bounded. Prove that $f(x) = x$ for some $x \in \mathbb{R}$.
- (h) Suppose $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuous and periodic: $f(x + p) = f(x)$ for some $p > 0$. Prove that f is uniformly continuous on \mathbb{R} .
- (i) Prove that if f is uniformly continuous on a bounded set $S \subset \mathbb{R}$, then f is bounded on S .

Proof.

- (a) Let

$$g(x) = f(x) - x.$$

Then g is continuous on $[0, 1]$, and

$$g(0) = f(0) \geq 0, \quad g(1) = f(1) - 1 \leq 0.$$

By the Intermediate Value Theorem, there exists $c \in [0, 1]$ with $g(c) = 0$. Hence $f(c) = c$.

Then g is continuous, and

$$g(-M) = f(-M) + M \geq 0, \quad g(M) = f(M) - M \leq 0.$$

By the Intermediate Value Theorem, there exists $x \in [-M, M]$ with $g(x) = 0$. Hence $f(x) = x$.

- (h) Since f is continuous on the compact interval $[-p, 2p]$, it is uniformly continuous there. Let $\varepsilon > 0$, and choose $\delta_0 > 0$ such that

$$|u - v| < \delta_0, \quad u, v \in [-p, 2p] \implies |f(u) - f(v)| < \varepsilon.$$

Set $\delta = \min\{\delta_0, p\}$. Let $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$ with $|x - y| < \delta$. Choose $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ so that $x - kp \in [0, p]$. Then $y - kp \in [-p, 2p]$, because $|x - y| < p$. Also

$$|(x - kp) - (y - kp)| = |x - y| < \delta_0.$$

By periodicity,

$$|f(x) - f(y)| = |f(x - kp) - f(y - kp)| < \varepsilon.$$

Hence f is uniformly continuous on \mathbb{R} .

- (i) Suppose f is uniformly continuous on bounded S but unbounded. Choose $x_n \in S$ such that

$$|f(x_n)| > n.$$

Since S is bounded, Bolzano–Weierstrass gives a convergent subsequence (x_{n_k}) . Hence (x_{n_k}) is Cauchy. By uniform continuity, $(f(x_{n_k}))$ is Cauchy, so it is bounded. But $|f(x_{n_k})| > n_k$, which is impossible. Therefore f is bounded.

Exam Problem 11

- (a) Prove that the harmonic series diverges without using the integral test.
 (b) Prove the sequential characterization of continuity.
 (c) If $\liminf |a_n| = 0$, prove that there exists a subsequence (a_{n_k}) such that $\sum a_{n_k}$ converges.
 (d) Let (a_n) be a sequence of nonzero real numbers. Prove that

$$\liminf \left| \frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} \right| \leq \liminf |a_n|^{1/n} \leq \limsup |a_n|^{1/n} \leq \limsup \left| \frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} \right|.$$

Proof.

- (a) Group the terms:

$$1 + \frac{1}{2} + \left(\frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} \right) + \left(\frac{1}{5} + \cdots + \frac{1}{8} \right) + \cdots.$$

In the block

$$\frac{1}{2^{m-1} + 1} + \cdots + \frac{1}{2^m},$$

there are 2^{m-1} terms, and each term is at least $1/2^m$. Hence the block sum is at least

$$2^{m-1} \cdot \frac{1}{2^m} = \frac{1}{2}.$$

Therefore the partial sums exceed $1 + r/2$ after r blocks. This tends to $+\infty$. So the harmonic series diverges.

- (b) Assume first that f is continuous at x_0 . Let $x_n \rightarrow x_0$ with $x_n \in S$. Given $\varepsilon > 0$, choose $\delta > 0$ such that

$$|x - x_0| < \delta, \quad x \in S \implies |f(x) - f(x_0)| < \varepsilon.$$

Since $x_n \rightarrow x_0$, we have $|x_n - x_0| < \delta$ eventually, hence $|f(x_n) - f(x_0)| < \varepsilon$ eventually. Thus $f(x_n) \rightarrow f(x_0)$.

Conversely, assume that for every sequence $x_n \rightarrow x_0$ in S , we have $f(x_n) \rightarrow f(x_0)$. Suppose f is not continuous at x_0 . Then there exists $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ such that for every $\delta > 0$ there is $x \in S$ with

$$|x - x_0| < \delta, \quad |f(x) - f(x_0)| \geq \varepsilon_0.$$

For each n , choose $x_n \in S$ such that

$$|x_n - x_0| < \frac{1}{n}, \quad |f(x_n) - f(x_0)| \geq \varepsilon_0.$$

Then $x_n \rightarrow x_0$, but $f(x_n)$ does not converge to $f(x_0)$, a contradiction. Hence f is continuous at x_0 .

- (c) Since $\liminf |a_n| = 0$, for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ there are infinitely many n such that

$$|a_n| < 2^{-k}.$$

Choose $n_1 < n_2 < \cdots$ so that

$$|a_{n_k}| < 2^{-k}$$

for every k . Then

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |a_{n_k}| \leq \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2^{-k} < \infty.$$

Hence $\sum a_{n_k}$ converges absolutely, and therefore converges.

- (d) The middle inequality

$$\liminf |a_n|^{1/n} \leq \limsup |a_n|^{1/n}$$

is immediate. Let

$$\alpha = \limsup |a_n|^{1/n}, \quad L = \limsup \left| \frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} \right|.$$

If $L = \infty$, there is nothing to prove. Assume $L \in \mathbb{R}$, and fix $L_1 > L$. Then there exists N_0 such that

$$\left| \frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} \right| < L_1$$

for all $n \geq N_0$. For $n > N_0$,

$$|a_n| = \left| \frac{a_n}{a_{n-1}} \right| \left| \frac{a_{n-1}}{a_{n-2}} \right| \cdots \left| \frac{a_{N_0+1}}{a_{N_0}} \right| |a_{N_0}| \leq L_1^{n-N_0} |a_{N_0}|.$$

Therefore

$$|a_n|^{1/n} \leq L_1 \left(L_1^{-N_0} |a_{N_0}| \right)^{1/n}.$$

Since $c^{1/n} \rightarrow 1$ for every $c > 0$, taking \limsup gives $\alpha \leq L_1$. Since $L_1 > L$ was arbitrary,

$$\limsup |a_n|^{1/n} \leq \limsup \left| \frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} \right|.$$

Now let

$$\beta = \liminf |a_n|^{1/n}, \quad \ell = \liminf \left| \frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} \right|.$$

If $\ell = 0$, then automatically $\ell \leq \beta$. Assume $\ell > 0$, and fix $0 < \ell_1 < \ell$. Then there exists N_0 such that

$$\left| \frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} \right| > \ell_1$$

for all $n \geq N_0$. For $n > N_0$,

$$|a_n| = \left| \frac{a_n}{a_{n-1}} \right| \left| \frac{a_{n-1}}{a_{n-2}} \right| \cdots \left| \frac{a_{N_0+1}}{a_{N_0}} \right| |a_{N_0}| \geq \ell_1^{n-N_0} |a_{N_0}|.$$

Hence

$$|a_n|^{1/n} \geq \ell_1 \left(\ell_1^{-N_0} |a_{N_0}| \right)^{1/n}.$$

Taking \liminf gives $\beta \geq \ell_1$. Since $0 < \ell_1 < \ell$ was arbitrary,

$$\liminf \left| \frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} \right| \leq \liminf |a_n|^{1/n}.$$

Combining the inequalities yields

$$\liminf \left| \frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} \right| \leq \liminf |a_n|^{1/n} \leq \limsup |a_n|^{1/n} \leq \limsup \left| \frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} \right|.$$

Real Analysis Practice Final Exam B

Problem 1.

(a) Define

$$a_1 = 1, \quad a_{n+1} = a_n + a_{n-1} + \cdots + a_1 + 1 \quad (n \geq 1).$$

Prove that

$$a_n = 2^{n-1} \quad \text{for every } n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

(b) Prove that

$$\sqrt{2} \notin \mathbb{Q}.$$

(c) Let $S \subset \mathbb{R}$ be nonempty and bounded below. Prove that a number $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ satisfies

$$\alpha = \inf S$$

if and only if the following two conditions hold:

$$(i) \alpha \leq s \text{ for all } s \in S,$$

$$(ii) \text{ for every } \epsilon > 0 \text{ there exists } s_\epsilon \in S \text{ with } s_\epsilon < \alpha + \epsilon.$$

(d) Show that the interval $(0, 1)$ has no maximum and no minimum, but

$$\inf(0, 1) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \sup(0, 1) = 1.$$

Problem 2.

(a) Let $p > 0$. Using the definition of limit, prove that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^p} = 0.$$

(b) Let $a \in \mathbb{R}$ satisfy $|a| < 1$. Using the definition of limit, prove that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a^n = 0.$$

(c) Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence of nonnegative real numbers and suppose that

$$s_n \rightarrow s.$$

Prove that $s \geq 0$.

(d) Under the assumptions of part (c), prove that

$$\sqrt{s_n} \rightarrow \sqrt{s}.$$

(e) Compute

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{3n^3 - 7n + 1}{5n^3 + 2n^2 + 2}.$$

Justify your answer carefully.

Problem 3.

(a) Let

$$s_n = \sum_{k=1}^n 3 \cdot 10^{-k}.$$

Prove that $s_n \rightarrow \frac{1}{3}$. In particular, prove that

$$0.3333 \cdots = \frac{1}{3}.$$

(b) Prove the following statement: if $\{s_n\}$ is increasing and unbounded, then

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} s_n = +\infty.$$

Deduce that if $\{s_n\}$ is decreasing and unbounded below, then

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} s_n = -\infty.$$

(c) Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence. Assume that $\lim s_n = L$ exists, where L may be a real number, $+\infty$, or $-\infty$. Prove that

$$\liminf s_n = L = \limsup s_n.$$

(d) Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence. Assume that

$$\liminf s_n = \limsup s_n = A,$$

where A may be a real number, $+\infty$, or $-\infty$. Prove that

$$\lim s_n = A.$$

(e) For the sequence

$$u_n = (-1)^n,$$

compute $\liminf u_n$ and $\limsup u_n$.

(f) For the sequence

$$v_n = \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{4}\right),$$

find all subsequential limits, and compute $\liminf v_n$ and $\limsup v_n$.

Problem 4.

(a) Prove that every bounded sequence of real numbers has a convergent subsequence.

(b) Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence that is not bounded from above. Prove that it has a strictly increasing subsequence diverging to $+\infty$.

(c) Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence that is not bounded from below. Prove that it has a strictly decreasing subsequence diverging to $-\infty$.

(d) Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence of real numbers and let $t \in \mathbb{R}$. Suppose that for every $\epsilon > 0$, the set

$$E_\epsilon := \{n \in \mathbb{N} : |s_n - t| < \epsilon\}$$

is infinite. Prove that $\{s_n\}$ has a subsequence converging to t .

(e) Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence of positive real numbers such that

$$\inf\{s_n : n \in \mathbb{N}\} = 0.$$

Prove that $\{s_n\}$ has a subsequence converging to 0.

(f) Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence. Prove that there exists a monotonic subsequence whose limit is $\limsup s_n$.

(g) Let $\{s_n\}$ be a sequence. Prove that there exists a monotonic subsequence whose limit is $\liminf s_n$.

Problem 5.

(a) Prove that the series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n$$

converges if and only if for every $\epsilon > 0$ there exists $N \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\left| \sum_{k=m}^n a_k \right| < \epsilon \quad \text{for all } n \geq m > N.$$

- (b) Let $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n$ be a series with $a_n \geq 0$ for all n . Assume that $\sum a_n$ converges, and let $\{b_n\}$ satisfy

$$|b_n| \leq a_n \quad \text{for all } n.$$

Prove that

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} b_n$$

converges.

- (c) Let $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n$ be a series with $a_n \geq 0$ for all n . Assume that

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n = +\infty,$$

and let $\{b_n\}$ satisfy

$$b_n \geq a_n \quad \text{for all } n.$$

Prove that

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} b_n = +\infty.$$

- (d) Determine whether the series

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{k^2}{3k^3 + 2}$$

converges or diverges. Justify your answer.

- (e) Determine whether the series

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{2k^3}{7^k}$$

converges or diverges. Give one proof using the ratio test and one proof using the root test.

Problem 6.

- (a) Let p be a real number with $0 < p \leq 1$. Prove that

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^p}$$

diverges to $+\infty$.

- (b) Let $p > 1$. Prove that

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^p}$$

converges.

- (c) Let $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k$ be a series. Suppose there is a locally integrable, nonnegative, decreasing function f on $[1, \infty)$ such that

$$f(k) = a_k \quad \text{for all } k \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Prove that if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_1^n f(x) dx = +\infty,$$

then

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k = +\infty.$$

- (d) Under the assumptions of part (c), prove that if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_1^n f(x) dx$$

exists and is finite, then

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k$$

converges.

Problem 7.

- (a) Let $\{a_n\}$ be a nonnegative decreasing sequence with $a_n \rightarrow 0$, and define

$$s_n = \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k+1} a_k.$$

Prove that the sequence $\{s_{2n}\}$ is increasing.

- (b) Under the assumptions of part (a), prove that the sequence $\{s_{2n+1}\}$ is decreasing.

- (c) Under the assumptions of part (a), prove that

$$s_{2m} \leq s_{2n+1} \quad \text{for all } m, n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

- (d) Deduce that the alternating series

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{k+1} a_k$$

converges.

- (e) If

$$s = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{k+1} a_k,$$

prove that

$$|s - s_n| < a_n \quad \text{for every } n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

- (f) Use the previous parts to show that

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+1} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$$

converges, but

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$$

diverges.

- (g) Let

$$s = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+1} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}.$$

Find an integer N that guarantees

$$|s - s_N| < 10^{-2}.$$

Problem 8.

- (a) Let $\alpha > 0$, and define

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} x^\alpha \sin\left(\frac{1}{x}\right), & x > 0, \\ 0, & x = 0. \end{cases}$$

Prove that f is continuous at 0.

- (b) Let H be the Heaviside function

$$H(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & x \geq 0, \\ 0, & x < 0. \end{cases}$$

Prove that H is not continuous at 0.

- (c) Let f and g be real-valued functions continuous at $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}$. Prove that $f + g$ is continuous at x_0 .

- (d) Under the assumptions of part (c), prove that fg is continuous at x_0 .
- (e) Under the assumptions of part (c), assume in addition that $g(x_0) \neq 0$ and that $g(x) \neq 0$ for all x in the domain of f/g sufficiently near x_0 . Prove that f/g is continuous at x_0 .
- (f) Let f be continuous at x_0 , and let g be continuous at $f(x_0)$. Prove that $g \circ f$ is continuous at x_0 .
- (g) Using the continuity of $x \mapsto |x|$ and part (f), prove that if f is continuous at x_0 , then $|f|$ is continuous at x_0 .
- (h) Using

$$\max\{f, g\} = \frac{1}{2}(f + g) + \frac{1}{2}|f - g|,$$

$$\min\{f, g\} = \frac{1}{2}(f + g) - \frac{1}{2}|f - g|,$$

prove that if f and g are continuous at x_0 , then $\max\{f, g\}$ and $\min\{f, g\}$ are continuous at x_0 .

Problem 9.

- (a) Prove that every continuous real-valued function on a closed interval $[a, b]$ is bounded.
- (b) Prove that every continuous real-valued function on a closed interval $[a, b]$ attains both a maximum and a minimum on $[a, b]$.
- (c) Prove the following statement: if f is continuous on $[a, b]$ and y lies strictly between $f(a)$ and $f(b)$, then there exists $x \in (a, b)$ such that $f(x) = y$.
- (d) Let g be a strictly increasing function on an interval J , and suppose that $g(J)$ is an interval. Prove that g is continuous on J .
- (e) Let f be a continuous strictly increasing function on an interval I . Prove that its inverse

$$f^{-1} : f(I) \rightarrow I$$

is continuous and strictly increasing.

Problem 10.

- (a) Let $a > 0$. Prove that the function

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{x}$$

is uniformly continuous on (a, ∞) .

- (b) Prove that $\sin x$ is uniformly continuous on \mathbb{R} .
- (c) Prove that the function

$$f(x) = \sin\left(\frac{1}{x^2}\right)$$

is not uniformly continuous on $(0, 1]$.

- (d) Prove that every continuous function on a closed interval $[a, b]$ is uniformly continuous on $[a, b]$.
- (e) Suppose that $f : (a, b) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ admits a continuous extension

$$\tilde{f} : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}.$$

Prove that f is uniformly continuous on (a, b) .

- (f) Suppose that $f : (a, b) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is uniformly continuous, and let $\{s_n\} \subset (a, b)$ satisfy

$$s_n \rightarrow a.$$

Prove that the sequence $\{f(s_n)\}$ converges in \mathbb{R} .

- (g) Under the assumptions of part (f), show that the limit in part (f) is independent of the choice of the sequence $\{s_n\}$. Define $f(a)$ and, similarly, $f(b)$, and deduce that f extends to a continuous function on $[a, b]$.
- (h) Let

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{x} \quad (x > 0).$$

Give a Cauchy sequence $\{s_n\} \subset (0, \infty)$ such that $\{f(s_n)\}$ is not Cauchy.

Problem 11.

- (a) Let $S \subset \mathbb{R} \setminus \{a\}$, let a be a limit point of S , and let $L \in \mathbb{R}$. Prove that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} f(x) = L$$

if and only if for every $\epsilon > 0$ there exists $\delta > 0$ such that

$$|f(x) - L| < \epsilon \quad \text{for all } x \in S \text{ with } |x - a| < \delta.$$

- (b) Prove that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{x^2} = +\infty.$$

- (c) Prove that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow (\pi/2)^+} \tan x = -\infty.$$

- (d) Let f_1 and f_2 be functions on S such that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} f_1(x) = L_1, \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} f_2(x) = L_2,$$

where $L_1, L_2 \in \mathbb{R}$. Prove that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} (f_1 + f_2)(x) = L_1 + L_2.$$

- (e) Under the assumptions of part (d), prove that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} (f_1 f_2)(x) = L_1 L_2.$$

- (f) Under the assumptions of part (d), assume in addition that $L_2 \neq 0$ and that $f_2(x) \neq 0$ for all $x \in S$. Prove that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} \frac{f_1(x)}{f_2(x)} = \frac{L_1}{L_2}.$$

- (g) Let $f : S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfy

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} f(x) = L \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Let g be defined on $f(S) \cup \{L\}$ and continuous at L . Prove that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} (g \circ f)(x) = g(L).$$

- (h) Let J be an open interval containing a , and let

$$f : J \setminus \{a\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}.$$

Prove that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a} f(x) = L$$

for some $L \in \mathbb{R}$ if and only if both one-sided limits

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a^-} f(x) \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow a^+} f(x)$$

exist and are equal to L .

End of Exam

Solutions

Problem 1

Key facts.

- Strong induction is the right tool for recursions involving all previous terms.
- $\alpha = \inf S$ iff α is a lower bound and elements of S come arbitrarily close to α from above.
- To show an open interval has no max/min, move inward: $x/2$ and $(x+1)/2$.

Canonical example. The exact lecture patterns are the strong-induction proof for $a_{n+1} = a_n + \dots + a_1 + 1$, the contradiction proof for $\sqrt{2} \notin \mathbb{Q}$, and the model set $(0, 1)$.

Model proof pattern.

(a) Base case:

$$a_1 = 1 = 2^0.$$

Inductive step: assume $a_k = 2^{k-1}$ for every $1 \leq k \leq n$. Then

$$a_{n+1} = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k + 1 = \sum_{k=1}^n 2^{k-1} + 1 = (2^n - 1) + 1 = 2^n.$$

So $a_n = 2^{n-1}$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

(b) Assume $\sqrt{2} = p/q$ with integers $p, q \neq 0$ having no common factor. Then

$$p^2 = 2q^2.$$

Hence p^2 is even, so $p = 2r$. Substituting,

$$4r^2 = 2q^2, \quad q^2 = 2r^2,$$

so q is also even. Thus p, q have common factor 2, contradiction.

(c) (\Rightarrow) If $\alpha = \inf S$, then $\alpha \leq s$ for all $s \in S$. If some $\varepsilon > 0$ satisfied $s \geq \alpha + \varepsilon$ for all $s \in S$, then $\alpha + \varepsilon$ would be a lower bound larger than α , impossible.

(\Leftarrow) Let $\beta = \inf S$. From (i), $\alpha \leq \beta$. If $\alpha < \beta$, let $\varepsilon = \beta - \alpha > 0$. By (ii) there is $s_\varepsilon \in S$ with

$$s_\varepsilon < \alpha + \varepsilon = \beta,$$

contradicting that β is a lower bound. Hence $\alpha = \beta = \inf S$.

(d) No maximum: if $x \in (0, 1)$, then

$$\frac{x+1}{2} \in (0, 1), \quad \frac{x+1}{2} > x.$$

No minimum: if $x \in (0, 1)$, then

$$\frac{x}{2} \in (0, 1), \quad \frac{x}{2} < x.$$

Also $0 < x < 1$ for every $x \in (0, 1)$, so 0 is a lower bound and 1 is an upper bound. If $\beta > 0$, then

$$s = \min\{\beta/2, 1/2\} \in (0, 1), \quad s < \beta,$$

so β is not a lower bound. Thus $\inf(0, 1) = 0$. If $\gamma < 1$, set

$$t = \frac{\max\{\gamma, 0\} + 1}{2}.$$

Then $t \in (0, 1)$ and $t > \gamma$, so γ is not an upper bound. Thus $\sup(0, 1) = 1$.

Problem 2

Key facts.

- In a direct ε -proof, solve the target inequality for n .
- A limit of nonnegative terms cannot be negative.
- For square roots, rationalize; for rational functions, divide

by the top power of n .

Canonical example. The exact lecture models are $1/n^p \rightarrow 0$, $a^n \rightarrow 0$ for $|a| < 1$, nonnegative limits, $\sqrt{s_n} \rightarrow \sqrt{s}$, and the rational-function limit $\frac{3n^3 - 7n + 1}{5n^3 + 2n^2 + 2} \rightarrow \frac{3}{5}$.

Model proof pattern.

(a) Given $\varepsilon > 0$, take $N = \varepsilon^{-1/p}$. Then $n > N$ implies

$$\left| \frac{1}{n^p} - 0 \right| = \frac{1}{n^p} < \varepsilon.$$

(b) Since $|a| < 1$, we have $\log|a| < 0$. Given $\varepsilon > 0$, take $N = \log \varepsilon / \log|a|$ (or $N = 0$ when $\varepsilon \geq 1$). Then $n > N$ gives

$$|a^n| = |a|^n < \varepsilon,$$

so $a^n \rightarrow 0$.

(c) Suppose $s < 0$. Take $\varepsilon = |s|/2$. Since $s_n \rightarrow s$, eventually

$$|s_n - s| < |s|/2,$$

hence

$$s_n < s + |s|/2 = -|s|/2 < 0,$$

contradicting $s_n \geq 0$. Therefore $s \geq 0$.

(d) If $s > 0$, choose N so that $|s_n - s| < \sqrt{s}\varepsilon$ for $n > N$. Then

$$|\sqrt{s_n} - \sqrt{s}| = \frac{|s_n - s|}{\sqrt{s_n} + \sqrt{s}} \leq \frac{|s_n - s|}{\sqrt{s}} < \varepsilon.$$

If $s = 0$, choose N so that $|s_n| < \varepsilon^2$ for $n > N$. Then

$$|\sqrt{s_n} - 0| = \sqrt{s_n} < \varepsilon.$$

(e) Write

$$\frac{3n^3 - 7n + 1}{5n^3 + 2n^2 + 2} = \frac{3 - \frac{7}{n^2} + \frac{1}{n^3}}{5 + \frac{2}{n} + \frac{2}{n^3}}.$$

Now

$$\frac{1}{n^2} \rightarrow 0, \quad \frac{1}{n} \rightarrow 0, \quad \frac{1}{n^3} \rightarrow 0,$$

so the numerator tends to 3 and the denominator tends to 5 $\neq 0$. Hence

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{3n^3 - 7n + 1}{5n^3 + 2n^2 + 2} = \frac{3}{5}.$$

Problem 3

Key facts.

- Bounded monotone sequences converge; unbounded monotone sequences diverge to $\pm\infty$.
- \liminf and \limsup are limits of tail infima and tail suprema.
- Periodic sequences are controlled by one period.

Canonical example. The lecture prototypes are the decimal $0.3333\dots$, the theorem on unbounded monotone sequences, and the standard computations for $(-1)^n$ and $\sin(n\pi/4)$.

Model proof pattern.

(a) Let

$$s_n = \sum_{k=1}^n 3 \cdot 10^{-k}.$$

Then s_n is increasing because every new term is positive. Also

$$s_n \leq \sum_{k=1}^n 9 \cdot 10^{-k} < 1,$$

so (s_n) is bounded. Hence $s_n \rightarrow L$ for some $L \in \mathbb{R}$. Since

$$\frac{s_n}{10} = s_{n+1} - \frac{3}{10},$$

passing to the limit gives

$$\frac{L}{10} = L - \frac{3}{10}.$$

Thus $L = 1/3$, so

$$0.3333 \dots = \lim s_n = \frac{1}{3}.$$

- (b) If (s_n) is increasing and unbounded, then for any $M > 0$ there is N with $s_N > M$. Since the sequence is increasing,

$$n > N \implies s_n \geq s_N > M.$$

Hence $s_n \rightarrow +\infty$. If (s_n) is decreasing and unbounded below, then $(-s_n)$ is increasing and unbounded above, so $-s_n \rightarrow +\infty$, i.e.

$$s_n \rightarrow -\infty.$$

- (c) If $\lim s_n = L$, there are three cases.

If $L \in \mathbb{R}$, then for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there is N_0 such that

$$L - \varepsilon < s_n < L + \varepsilon \quad (n > N_0).$$

Hence tail suprema satisfy $\sup\{s_n : n > N_0\} \leq L + \varepsilon$, and tail infima satisfy $\inf\{s_n : n > N_0\} \geq L - \varepsilon$. Therefore

$$\limsup s_n \leq L + \varepsilon, \quad \liminf s_n \geq L - \varepsilon.$$

Send $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$.

If $L = +\infty$, then for every $M > 0$, eventually $s_n > M$, so eventually every tail infimum is at least M . Thus

$$\liminf s_n = +\infty = \limsup s_n.$$

If $L = -\infty$, apply the previous argument to $-s_n$.

- (d) Again split into three cases.

If $A \in \mathbb{R}$, then given $\varepsilon > 0$ choose N_0, N_1 so that

$$\sup\{s_n : n > N_0\} < A + \varepsilon, \quad \inf\{s_n : n > N_1\} > A - \varepsilon.$$

Thus for $n > \max\{N_0, N_1\}$,

$$A - \varepsilon < s_n < A + \varepsilon.$$

Hence $s_n \rightarrow A$.

If $A = +\infty$, then for every $M > 0$ the tail infima are eventually $> M$, so eventually $s_n > M$; hence $s_n \rightarrow +\infty$. The case $A = -\infty$ is analogous.

- (e) For every N ,

$$\inf\{(-1)^n : n > N\} = -1, \quad \sup\{(-1)^n : n > N\} = 1.$$

Therefore

$$\liminf(-1)^n = -1, \quad \limsup(-1)^n = 1.$$

- (f) The values of

$$v_n = \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{4}\right)$$

repeat with period 8:

$$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}, 1, \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}, 0, -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}, -1, -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}, 0, \dots$$

Hence each of

$$-1, -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}, 0, \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}, 1$$

occurs infinitely often, so each is a subsequential limit. There are no others because every convergent subsequence of a finite-valued sequence must eventually be constant. Thus

$$\{\text{subsequential limits}\} = \left\{-1, -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}, 0, \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}, 1\right\},$$

and therefore

$$\liminf v_n = -1, \quad \limsup v_n = 1.$$

Problem 4

Key facts.

- Every sequence has a monotone subsequence.
- If terms enter every shrinking neighborhood infinitely often, diagonalize with $|s_{n_k} - t| < 1/k$.
- \limsup and \liminf are realized by subsequences.

Canonical example. The exact lecture patterns are the dominant-term proof of Bolzano–Weierstrass, the inductive construction of subsequences going to $\pm\infty$, and the diagonal subsequence argument.

Model proof pattern.

- (a) Every sequence has a monotone subsequence: either there are infinitely many dominant terms, which give a decreasing subsequence, or only finitely many, after which one constructs an increasing subsequence. Now apply this to a bounded sequence. The monotone subsequence is still bounded, hence convergent by the monotone convergence theorem.
- (b) Since (s_n) is not bounded above, choose n_1 with $s_{n_1} > 1$. After choosing

$$n_1 < \dots < n_{k-1}$$

with

$$s_{n_1} < \dots < s_{n_{k-1}}, \quad s_{n_j} > j,$$

pick n_k so that

$$s_{n_k} > \max\{s_1, \dots, s_{n_{k-1}}, k\}.$$

Then $n_k > n_{k-1}$, $s_{n_k} > s_{n_{k-1}}$, and $s_{n_k} > k$. Hence (s_{n_k}) is strictly increasing and $s_{n_k} \rightarrow +\infty$.

- (c) Apply part (b) to $(-s_n)$. Then $(-s_{n_k})$ has a strictly increasing subsequence tending to $+\infty$, so (s_{n_k}) is strictly decreasing and tends to $-\infty$.
- (d) For each k , the set

$$E_{1/k} = \{n \in \mathbb{N} : |s_n - t| < 1/k\}$$

is infinite, hence nonempty. Choose $n_1 \in E_1$. Having chosen n_{k-1} , choose

$$n_k > n_{k-1} \quad \text{with} \quad n_k \in E_{1/k}.$$

Then

$$|s_{n_k} - t| < \frac{1}{k} \rightarrow 0,$$

so $s_{n_k} \rightarrow t$.

- (e) Since $\inf\{s_n : n \in \mathbb{N}\} = 0$ and each $s_n > 0$, for every $\varepsilon > 0$ the set

$$\{n : s_n < \varepsilon\}$$

must be infinite. Otherwise there would be $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ such that only finitely many terms lie below ε_0 ; the finite set of those positive terms has a positive minimum, and all remaining terms are at least ε_0 , giving a positive lower bound for the whole sequence. This contradicts the infimum being 0. Now apply part (d) with $t = 0$.

- (f) Let $t = \limsup s_n$.

If $t = +\infty$, use part (b): there is a strictly increasing subsequence tending to $+\infty = t$.

If $t = -\infty$, then (s_n) is not bounded below. By part (c), there is a strictly decreasing subsequence tending to $-\infty = t$. If $t \in \mathbb{R}$, fix $\varepsilon > 0$. Since tail suprema converge to t , there is N_0 such that

$$\sup\{s_n : n > N\} < t + \varepsilon \quad (N \geq N_0).$$

So $s_n < t + \varepsilon$ for all $n > N_0$. If the set

$$\{n : t - \varepsilon < s_n < t + \varepsilon\}$$

were finite, then for some $N_1 > N_0$ we would have $s_n \leq t - \varepsilon$ for all $n > N_1$, forcing

$$\sup\{s_n : n > N_1\} \leq t - \varepsilon,$$

contradiction. Hence every ε -neighborhood of t contains infinitely many terms. By part (d), there is a subsequence converging to t . Now take a monotone subsequence of that subsequence; it still converges to t .

- (g) Apply part (f) to $(-s_n)$. There is a monotone subsequence $(-s_{n_k})$ converging to

$$\limsup(-s_n) = -\liminf s_n.$$

Multiplying by -1 , the subsequence (s_{n_k}) is monotone and converges to

$$-\limsup(-s_n) = \liminf s_n.$$

Problem 5

Key facts.

- A series converges iff its tails are arbitrarily small.
- For nonnegative comparison, prove upper bounds for convergence and lower bounds for divergence.
- Ratio and root tests detect geometric decay.

Canonical example. The exact lecture examples are $\sum \frac{k^2}{3k^3+2}$ by comparison with $\sum \frac{1}{k}$, and $\sum \frac{2k^3}{7^k}$ by both the ratio and root tests.

Model proof pattern.

- (a) Let

$$s_n = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k \quad (n \geq 1),$$

and set $s_0 = 0$. Then for $n \geq m$,

$$s_n - s_{m-1} = \sum_{k=m}^n a_k.$$

So the condition

$$\left| \sum_{k=m}^n a_k \right| < \varepsilon \quad (n \geq m > N)$$

is exactly the statement that the partial sums (s_n) form a Cauchy sequence. By the Cauchy criterion for sequences, (s_n) converges iff it is Cauchy. Hence the series converges iff the displayed tail condition holds.

- (b) Since $a_n \geq 0$ and $\sum a_n$ converges, its tails satisfy

$$\sum_{k=m}^n a_k < \varepsilon$$

for all $n \geq m > N$, once N is large enough. Then

$$\left| \sum_{k=m}^n b_k \right| \leq \sum_{k=m}^n |b_k| \leq \sum_{k=m}^n a_k < \varepsilon.$$

Thus $\sum b_n$ satisfies the Cauchy criterion and therefore converges.

- (c) Let

$$s_n = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k, \quad t_n = \sum_{k=1}^n b_k.$$

Since $b_k \geq a_k \geq 0$,

$$t_n \geq s_n \quad \text{for all } n.$$

Given $M > 0$, choose N so that $s_n > M$ for all $n > N$ (because $\sum a_n = +\infty$). Then

$$t_n \geq s_n > M \quad (n > N).$$

Hence $\sum b_n = +\infty$.

- (d) For $k \geq 1$,

$$3k^3 + 2 \leq 5k^3,$$

so

$$\frac{k^2}{3k^3 + 2} \geq \frac{k^2}{5k^3} = \frac{1}{5k}.$$

Since

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{5k}$$

diverges, the comparison test gives divergence of

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{k^2}{3k^3 + 2}.$$

- (e) Let

$$a_k = \frac{2k^3}{7^k}.$$

Ratio test:

$$\frac{a_{k+1}}{a_k} = \frac{2(k+1)^3/7^{k+1}}{2k^3/7^k} = \frac{(k+1)^3}{7k^3} = \frac{1}{7} \left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right)^3 \rightarrow \frac{1}{7} < 1.$$

So the series converges.

Root test:

$$a_k^{1/k} = \left(\frac{2k^3}{7^k}\right)^{1/k} = 2^{1/k} (k^{1/k})^3 \cdot \frac{1}{7} \rightarrow 1 \cdot 1^3 \cdot \frac{1}{7} = \frac{1}{7} < 1.$$

So the series also converges by the root test.

Problem 6

Key facts.

- For positive decreasing terms, compare partial sums with areas of rectangles.
- Partial sums of a nonnegative series form an increasing sequence.
- The integral test is a monotone-comparison argument in disguise.

Canonical example. The lecture proofs for the p -series are the exact templates for the general integral test.

Model proof pattern.

- (a) Let

$$s_n = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k^p}.$$

Since $x \mapsto x^{-p}$ is decreasing on $(0, \infty)$,

$$s_n = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_k^{k+1} \frac{1}{k^p} dx \geq \int_1^{n+1} \frac{dx}{x^p}.$$

If $p = 1$, the integral equals $\log(n+1) \rightarrow +\infty$. If $0 < p < 1$, then

$$\int_1^{n+1} \frac{dx}{x^p} = \frac{(n+1)^{1-p} - 1}{1-p} \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Hence $s_n \rightarrow +\infty$, so

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^p} = +\infty \quad (0 < p \leq 1).$$

(b) Again let

$$s_n = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k^p}.$$

This sequence is increasing. Also, since $x \mapsto x^{-p}$ is decreasing,

$$s_n = 1 + \sum_{k=2}^n \int_{k-1}^k \frac{1}{k^p} dx \leq 1 + \int_1^n \frac{dx}{x^p}.$$

For $p > 1$,

$$\int_1^n \frac{dx}{x^p} = \frac{1 - n^{1-p}}{p-1} < \frac{1}{p-1},$$

so (s_n) is bounded above. Therefore (s_n) converges, and

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^p}$$

converges for $p > 1$.

(c) Let

$$s_n = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k.$$

Since $a_k = f(k)$ and f is decreasing,

$$s_n = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_k^{k+1} f(k) dx \geq \int_1^{n+1} f(x) dx.$$

If

$$\int_1^n f(x) dx \rightarrow +\infty,$$

then the right-hand side tends to $+\infty$, so $s_n \rightarrow +\infty$. Hence

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k = +\infty.$$

(d) Because $a_k \geq 0$, the partial sums

$$s_n = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k$$

are increasing. Also,

$$s_n = a_1 + \sum_{k=2}^n \int_{k-1}^k f(k) dx \leq a_1 + \int_1^n f(x) dx.$$

If

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_1^n f(x) dx$$

exists and is finite, then (s_n) is bounded above. Hence (s_n) converges, so the series converges.

Problem 7

Key facts.

- Even partial sums go one way, odd partial sums go the other way.
- The even and odd subsequences squeeze the limit.
- The remainder is controlled by the first omitted term.

Canonical example. The lecture proof of the alternating series test is the exact model here, and $\sum (-1)^{n+1}/\sqrt{n}$ is its standard application.

Model proof pattern.

(a) For

$$s_n = \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k+1} a_k,$$

we have

$$s_{2n+2} - s_{2n} = a_{2n+1} - a_{2n+2} \geq 0$$

because (a_n) is decreasing. Hence (s_{2n}) is increasing.

(b) Similarly,

$$s_{2n+1} - s_{2n-1} = a_{2n+1} - a_{2n} \leq 0,$$

so (s_{2n+1}) is decreasing.

(c) If $m \leq n$, then

$$s_{2m} \leq s_{2n} \leq s_{2n+1}.$$

If $m > n$, then

$$s_{2m} \leq s_{2m+1} \leq s_{2n+1}.$$

So in all cases

$$s_{2m} \leq s_{2n+1}.$$

(d) By parts (a)–(c), (s_{2n}) is increasing and bounded above by every odd partial sum, while (s_{2n+1}) is decreasing and bounded below by every even partial sum. Hence both converge:

$$s_{2n} \rightarrow s, \quad s_{2n+1} \rightarrow t.$$

But

$$t - s = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (s_{2n+1} - s_{2n}) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_{2n+1} = 0.$$

So $s = t$. Therefore the whole sequence (s_n) converges.

(e) Let

$$s = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+1} a_n.$$

From the proof above,

$$s_{2k} \leq s \leq s_{2k+1}.$$

Hence the limit lies between consecutive partial sums, so the remainder has size at most the next jump. The lecture estimate is

$$|s - s_n| < a_n \quad (n \in \mathbb{N}).$$

(f) Take

$$a_n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}.$$

Then $a_n \geq 0$, (a_n) is decreasing, and $a_n \rightarrow 0$. By part (d),

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+1} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$$

converges. But

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$$

is a p -series with $p = \frac{1}{2} \leq 1$, so it diverges.

(g) By part (e),

$$|s - s_N| < \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}}.$$

So it is enough to choose N with

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} < 10^{-2}.$$

One choice is

$$N = 10001.$$

Problem 8

Key facts.

- Use either the sequential definition or the ε - δ definition.
- Continuity is preserved by $+$, \cdot , \div (when the denominator stays nonzero), and composition.
- Once $|x|$ is continuous, so are $|f|$, $\max\{f, g\}$, and $\min\{f, g\}$.

Canonical example. The lecture models are $x^\alpha \sin(1/x)$ at 0, the Heaviside jump at 0, and the continuity theorems for algebraic operations and composition.

Model proof pattern.

(a) Let

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} x^\alpha \sin(1/x), & x > 0, \\ 0, & x = 0. \end{cases}$$

Given $\varepsilon > 0$, choose $\delta = \varepsilon^{1/\alpha}$. If $0 \leq x < \delta$, then

$$|f(x) - f(0)| = |x^\alpha \sin(1/x)| \leq x^\alpha < \varepsilon.$$

So f is continuous at 0.

(b) Let $x_n = -1/n$. Then $x_n \rightarrow 0$, but

$$H(x_n) = 0 \quad \text{for all } n,$$

while

$$H(0) = 1.$$

Hence $H(x_n) \not\rightarrow H(0)$, so H is not continuous at 0.

(c) Let $x_n \rightarrow x_0$. Since f and g are continuous at x_0 ,

$$f(x_n) \rightarrow f(x_0), \quad g(x_n) \rightarrow g(x_0).$$

By the addition law for sequence limits,

$$(f+g)(x_n) = f(x_n) + g(x_n) \rightarrow f(x_0) + g(x_0) = (f+g)(x_0).$$

So $f+g$ is continuous at x_0 .

(d) With the same setup,

$$(fg)(x_n) = f(x_n)g(x_n) \rightarrow f(x_0)g(x_0) = (fg)(x_0),$$

by the multiplication law for sequences. Hence fg is continuous at x_0 .

(e) Assume $g(x_0) \neq 0$ and $g(x) \neq 0$ near x_0 . If $x_n \rightarrow x_0$ through points where f/g is defined, then

$$f(x_n) \rightarrow f(x_0), \quad g(x_n) \rightarrow g(x_0) \neq 0.$$

By the division law for sequence limits,

$$\frac{f(x_n)}{g(x_n)} \rightarrow \frac{f(x_0)}{g(x_0)}.$$

So f/g is continuous at x_0 .

(f) If $x_n \rightarrow x_0$, continuity of f gives

$$f(x_n) \rightarrow f(x_0).$$

Since g is continuous at $f(x_0)$,

$$g(f(x_n)) \rightarrow g(f(x_0)).$$

Thus

$$(g \circ f)(x_n) \rightarrow (g \circ f)(x_0),$$

so $g \circ f$ is continuous at x_0 .

(g) Let $h(x) = |x|$. The lecture proof shows h is continuous on \mathbb{R} . If f is continuous at x_0 , then by part (f),

$$|f| = h \circ f$$

is continuous at x_0 .

(h) Use

$$\max\{f, g\} = \frac{1}{2}(f+g) + \frac{1}{2}|f-g|, \quad \min\{f, g\} = \frac{1}{2}(f+g) - \frac{1}{2}|f-g|.$$

By parts (c) and (g), $f+g$ and $|f-g|$ are continuous at x_0 . Hence both $\max\{f, g\}$ and $\min\{f, g\}$ are continuous at x_0 .

Problem 9

Key facts.

- Continuous functions on $[a, b]$ are bounded and attain extrema.
- The IVT is proved by a supremum construction.
- A strictly monotone map with interval image is continuous, and so is its inverse.

Canonical example. The lecture proofs use Bolzano–Weierstrass for boundedness and extrema, the supremum set $S = \{t : f(t) < y\}$ for IVT, and the monotone-interval argument for inverse continuity.

Model proof pattern.

(a) Suppose f is unbounded on $[a, b]$. For each n choose $x_n \in [a, b]$ with

$$|f(x_n)| > n.$$

Since (x_n) is bounded, Bolzano–Weierstrass gives a subsequence $x_{n_k} \rightarrow x_0 \in [a, b]$. Continuity gives

$$f(x_{n_k}) \rightarrow f(x_0) \in \mathbb{R},$$

so $(|f(x_{n_k})|)$ is bounded. But $|f(x_{n_k})| > n_k \rightarrow \infty$, contradiction. Hence f is bounded.

(b) Let

$$M = \sup\{f(x) : x \in [a, b]\}.$$

For each n , choose $y_n \in [a, b]$ with

$$M - \frac{1}{n} < f(y_n) \leq M.$$

Then $f(y_n) \rightarrow M$. By Bolzano–Weierstrass, some subsequence $y_{n_k} \rightarrow y_0 \in [a, b]$. By continuity,

$$f(y_0) = \lim f(y_{n_k}) = M,$$

so f attains its maximum. Apply the same argument to $-f$ to get a minimum.

(c) Assume $f(a) < y < f(b)$ and let

$$S = \{t \in [a, b] : f(t) < y\}.$$

Then $a \in S$, $b \notin S$, so S is nonempty and bounded above. Let

$$x = \sup S.$$

Choose $s_n \in S$ with

$$x - \frac{1}{n} < s_n \leq x.$$

Then $s_n \rightarrow x$ and $f(s_n) < y$, so continuity gives

$$f(x) \leq y.$$

Now let

$$t_n = \min \left\{ b, x + \frac{1}{n} \right\}.$$

Since $t_n \notin S$, we have $f(t_n) \geq y$. Also $t_n \rightarrow x$, so continuity gives

$$f(x) \geq y.$$

Hence $f(x) = y$. Since $f(a) \neq y$ and $f(b) \neq y$, we have $x \neq a, b$, so $x \in (a, b)$.

(d) Let $x_0 \in J$. First suppose x_0 is not an endpoint of J . Since

g is strictly increasing and $g(J)$ is an interval, $g(x_0)$ is not an endpoint of $g(J)$. Choose $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ with

$$(g(x_0) - \varepsilon_0, g(x_0) + \varepsilon_0) \subset g(J).$$

Given $0 < \varepsilon < \varepsilon_0$, choose $x_1, x_2 \in J$ such that

$$g(x_1) = g(x_0) - \varepsilon, \quad g(x_2) = g(x_0) + \varepsilon.$$

Strict increase gives

$$x_1 < x_0 < x_2.$$

Let

$$\delta = \min\{x_0 - x_1, x_2 - x_0\}.$$

If $|x - x_0| < \delta$, then $x_1 < x < x_2$, so

$$g(x_0) - \varepsilon < g(x) < g(x_0) + \varepsilon.$$

Thus $|g(x) - g(x_0)| < \varepsilon$, proving continuity at x_0 . Endpoint cases are handled by the same one-sided argument.

- (e) Since f is continuous on the interval I , the image $f(I)$ is an interval by the IVT. Because f is strictly increasing, it is one-to-one, so f^{-1} is well-defined on $f(I)$. Also f^{-1} is strictly increasing: if $y_1 < y_2$ and

$$y_1 = f(x_1), \quad y_2 = f(x_2),$$

then strict increase of f forces $x_1 < x_2$, i.e.

$$f^{-1}(y_1) < f^{-1}(y_2).$$

Now apply part (d) to $g = f^{-1}$ on the interval $f(I)$. Since $g(f(I)) = I$ is an interval, f^{-1} is continuous.

Problem 10

Key facts.

- Uniform continuity uses one δ for all points in the domain.
- Continuous on a closed interval implies uniformly continuous.
- Uniform continuity sends Cauchy sequences to Cauchy sequences and is equivalent to continuous extendability on (a, b) .

Canonical example. The lecture prototypes are $1/x$ on (a, ∞) , $\sin x$ on \mathbb{R} , and $\sin(1/x^2)$ on $(0, 1]$; the endpoint-extension theorem is the exact model for parts (e)–(g).

Model proof pattern.

- (a) Fix $\varepsilon > 0$ and set

$$\delta = a^2\varepsilon.$$

If $x, y > a$ and $|x - y| < \delta$, then

$$\left| \frac{1}{x} - \frac{1}{y} \right| = \frac{|x - y|}{xy} \leq \frac{|x - y|}{a^2} < \frac{\delta}{a^2} = \varepsilon.$$

So $1/x$ is uniformly continuous on (a, ∞) .

- (b) For all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$\begin{aligned} |\sin x - \sin y| &= 2 \left| \cos\left(\frac{x+y}{2}\right) \sin\left(\frac{x-y}{2}\right) \right| \\ &\leq 2 \left| \sin\left(\frac{x-y}{2}\right) \right| \\ &\leq |x - y|. \end{aligned}$$

Given $\varepsilon > 0$, take $\delta = \varepsilon$. Then $|x - y| < \delta$ implies

$$|\sin x - \sin y| < \varepsilon.$$

Hence $\sin x$ is uniformly continuous on \mathbb{R} .

- (c) Let

$$a_n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi n}}, \quad b_n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi n + \pi/2}}.$$

Then $a_n, b_n \in (0, 1]$,

$$\sin\left(\frac{1}{a_n^2}\right) = \sin(2\pi n) = 0, \quad \sin\left(\frac{1}{b_n^2}\right) = \sin\left(2\pi n + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) = 1,$$

so

$$\left| \sin\left(\frac{1}{a_n^2}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{1}{b_n^2}\right) \right| = 1.$$

Also $|a_n - b_n| \rightarrow 0$. Therefore, for $\varepsilon_0 = 1$, every $\delta > 0$ fails the uniform-continuity condition once n is large. Hence $f(x) = \sin(1/x^2)$ is not uniformly continuous on $(0, 1]$.

- (d) Suppose f is continuous on $[a, b]$ but not uniformly continuous. Then there exists $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ such that for each n one can find $x_n, y_n \in [a, b]$ with

$$|x_n - y_n| < \frac{1}{n}, \quad |f(x_n) - f(y_n)| \geq \varepsilon_0.$$

By Bolzano–Weierstrass, some subsequence $x_{n_k} \rightarrow x_0 \in [a, b]$. Since

$$|y_{n_k} - x_0| \leq |y_{n_k} - x_{n_k}| + |x_{n_k} - x_0|,$$

we also have $y_{n_k} \rightarrow x_0$. Continuity of f at x_0 gives

$$f(x_{n_k}) \rightarrow f(x_0), \quad f(y_{n_k}) \rightarrow f(x_0),$$

so

$$|f(x_{n_k}) - f(y_{n_k})| \rightarrow 0,$$

contradicting the lower bound ε_0 .

- (e) If \tilde{f} is continuous on $[a, b]$, then by part (d) it is uniformly continuous on $[a, b]$. Restricting to the subset (a, b) shows that

$$f = \tilde{f}|_{(a,b)}$$

is uniformly continuous on (a, b) .

- (f) If $s_n \rightarrow a$ with $s_n \in (a, b)$, then (s_n) is Cauchy. Since f is uniformly continuous on (a, b) , Theorem 25.1 gives that $(f(s_n))$ is Cauchy. Every Cauchy sequence in \mathbb{R} converges, so $(f(s_n))$ converges.
- (g) Let $s_n, t_n \in (a, b)$ with

$$s_n \rightarrow a, \quad t_n \rightarrow a.$$

Interleave them:

$$u_1 = s_1, u_2 = t_1, u_3 = s_2, u_4 = t_2, \dots$$

Then $u_n \rightarrow a$. By part (f), $(f(u_n))$ converges. Since $(f(s_n))$ and $(f(t_n))$ are subsequences of $(f(u_n))$, they have the same limit. Thus the limit in part (f) is independent of the sequence approaching a .

Define

$$\tilde{f}(a) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(s_n)$$

for any sequence $s_n \rightarrow a$ in (a, b) , and define $\tilde{f}(b)$ similarly. Set $\tilde{f} = f$ on (a, b) . By construction, every sequence in (a, b) converging to a has image converging to $\tilde{f}(a)$, so \tilde{f} is continuous at a ; similarly at b . Also $\tilde{f} = f$ on (a, b) , and uniform continuity implies continuity there. Hence \tilde{f} is a continuous extension of f to $[a, b]$.

- (h) Take

$$s_n = \frac{1}{n}.$$

Then (s_n) is Cauchy in $(0, \infty)$, but

$$f(s_n) = \frac{1}{1/n} = n,$$

and (n) is not Cauchy. So this is the required counterexample.

Problem 11
Key facts.

- Function limits are proved either by sequences or by the ε - δ/M - δ criteria.
- Addition, multiplication, division, and composition reduce to the corresponding sequence limit theorems.
- A two-sided limit exists exactly when the one-sided limits exist and agree.

Canonical example. The lecture templates are $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} 1/x^2 = +\infty$, $\lim_{x \rightarrow (\pi/2)^+} \tan x = -\infty$, and the general limit laws for functions.

Model proof pattern.(a) (\Rightarrow) Assume

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} f(x) = L.$$

Let $\varepsilon > 0$. For contradiction, suppose no $\delta > 0$ works. Since a is a limit point of S , for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ there exists $x_n \in S$ with

$$|x_n - a| < \frac{1}{n}, \quad |f(x_n) - L| \geq \varepsilon.$$

Then $x_n \rightarrow a$ but $f(x_n) \not\rightarrow L$, contradiction. So the ε - δ condition holds.

(\Leftarrow) Assume the ε - δ condition. Let $x_n \in S$ with $x_n \rightarrow a$. Given $\varepsilon > 0$, choose $\delta > 0$ so that

$$|x - a| < \delta, x \in S \implies |f(x) - L| < \varepsilon.$$

Since $x_n \rightarrow a$, eventually $|x_n - a| < \delta$, hence eventually $|f(x_n) - L| < \varepsilon$. Therefore $f(x_n) \rightarrow L$, so

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} f(x) = L.$$

(b) To prove

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{x^2} = +\infty,$$

let $M > 0$ and choose

$$\delta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{M}}.$$

Then

$$0 < |x| < \delta \implies \frac{1}{x^2} > \frac{1}{\delta^2} = M.$$

Hence the limit is $+\infty$.

(c) To prove

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow (\pi/2)^+} \tan x = -\infty,$$

let $M > 0$. By continuity of \sin at $\pi/2$, choose $\delta_1 > 0$ so that

$$\frac{\pi}{2} < x < \frac{\pi}{2} + \delta_1 \implies \sin x > \frac{1}{2}.$$

By continuity of \cos at $\pi/2$, choose $\delta_2 > 0$ so that

$$\frac{\pi}{2} < x < \frac{\pi}{2} + \delta_2 \implies -\frac{1}{2M} < \cos x < 0.$$

Set $\delta = \min\{\delta_1, \delta_2\}$. Then

$$\frac{\pi}{2} < x < \frac{\pi}{2} + \delta \implies \sin x > \frac{1}{2}, \quad -\frac{1}{2M} < \cos x < 0.$$

Hence

$$\frac{1}{\cos x} < -2M, \quad \tan x = \sin x \cdot \frac{1}{\cos x} < \frac{1}{2}(-2M) = -M.$$

So the right-hand limit is $-\infty$.(d) Let $x_n \in S$ with $x_n \rightarrow a$. Then

$$f_1(x_n) \rightarrow L_1, \quad f_2(x_n) \rightarrow L_2.$$

By the sequence addition law,

$$(f_1 + f_2)(x_n) = f_1(x_n) + f_2(x_n) \rightarrow L_1 + L_2.$$

Since this holds for every such sequence,

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} (f_1 + f_2)(x) = L_1 + L_2.$$

(e) With the same reduction to sequences, the multiplication law gives

$$f_1(x_n)f_2(x_n) \rightarrow L_1L_2.$$

Therefore

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} (f_1f_2)(x) = L_1L_2.$$

(f) Again take $x_n \rightarrow a$ in S . Then

$$f_1(x_n) \rightarrow L_1, \quad f_2(x_n) \rightarrow L_2 \neq 0,$$

and $f_2(x_n) \neq 0$ for all n . By the sequence division law,

$$\frac{f_1(x_n)}{f_2(x_n)} \rightarrow \frac{L_1}{L_2}.$$

Hence

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} \frac{f_1(x)}{f_2(x)} = \frac{L_1}{L_2}.$$

(g) Let $x_n \in S$ with $x_n \rightarrow a$. Since

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} f(x) = L,$$

we have

$$f(x_n) \rightarrow L.$$

Because g is continuous at L ,

$$g(f(x_n)) \rightarrow g(L).$$

So

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a, x \in S} (g \circ f)(x) = g(L).$$

(h) (\Rightarrow) If $\lim_{x \rightarrow a} f(x) = L$, then every sequence approaching a from the left or right is in particular a sequence approaching a , so both one-sided limits exist and equal L . (\Leftarrow) Suppose

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a^-} f(x) = L = \lim_{x \rightarrow a^+} f(x).$$

Given $\varepsilon > 0$, choose $\delta_- > 0$ and $\delta_+ > 0$ such that

$$a - \delta_- < x < a \implies |f(x) - L| < \varepsilon,$$

$$a < x < a + \delta_+ \implies |f(x) - L| < \varepsilon.$$

Let

$$\delta = \min\{\delta_-, \delta_+\}.$$

Then

$$0 < |x - a| < \delta$$

implies either $a - \delta < x < a$ or $a < x < a + \delta$, and in either case $|f(x) - L| < \varepsilon$. Hence

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow a} f(x) = L.$$

Solutions (Version B references)

Exam Part	Lecture Source	Exam Part	Lecture Source
1(a)	Lecture 1 Example 1.2	6(c)	Lecture 18 Theorem 18.3
1(b)	Lecture 1 Example 1.4	6(d)	Lecture 18 Theorem 18.3
1(c)	Lecture 3 Proposition 3.6	7(a)	Lecture 19 Theorem 19.2
1(d)	Lecture 3 Example 3.4	7(b)	Lecture 19 Theorem 19.2
2(a)	Lecture 6 Example 6.3	7(c)	Lecture 19 Theorem 19.2
2(b)	Lecture 6 Example 6.4	7(d)	Lecture 19 Theorem 19.2
2(c)	Lecture 6 Example 6.5	7(e)	Lecture 19 Theorem 19.2
2(d)	Lecture 6 Example 6.5	7(f)	Lecture 19 Example 19.1; Theorem 19.2
2(e)	Lecture 7 Example 7.6	7(g)	Lecture 19 Theorem 19.2
3(a)	Lecture 9 Example 9.5	8(a)	Lecture 20 Example 20.5
3(b)	Lecture 9 Theorem 9.6	8(b)	Lecture 20 Example 20.6
3(c)	Lecture 9 Theorem 9.9	8(c)	Lecture 21 Theorem 21.1
3(d)	Lecture 9 Theorem 9.9	8(d)	Lecture 21 Theorem 21.1
3(e)	Lecture 9 Example 9.8	8(e)	Lecture 21 Theorem 21.1
3(f)	Lecture 12 Example 12.2; Lecture 9 Example 9.8	8(f)	Lecture 21 Theorem 21.2
4(a)	Lecture 13 Theorem 13.1	8(g)	Lecture 20+21 Example 20.4 and Thm 21.2
4(b)	Lecture 12 Proposition 12.3	8(h)	Lecture 21 Corollary 21.4
4(c)	Lecture 12 Proposition 12.3	9(a)	Lecture 22 Theorem 22.1
4(d)	Lecture 12 Proposition 12.4	9(b)	Lecture 22 Theorem 22.3
4(e)	Lecture 12 Example 12.5	9(c)	Lecture 22 Theorem 22.5
4(f)	Lecture 13 Theorem 13.3	9(d)	Lecture 23 Theorem 23.4
4(g)	Lecture 13 Theorem 13.3	9(e)	Lecture 23 Theorem 23.5
5(a)	Lecture 15 Theorem 15.4	10(a)	Lecture 24 Example 24.5
5(b)	Lecture 16 Theorem 16.2	10(b)	Lecture 24 Example 24.6
5(c)	Lecture 16 Theorem 16.2	10(c)	Lecture 24 Example 24.7
5(d)	Lecture 16 Example 16.4	10(d)	Lecture 24 Theorem 24.8
5(e)	Lecture 17 Example 17.7	10(e)	Lecture 25 Theorem 25.5
6(a)	Lecture 18 Example 18.1	10(f)	Lecture 25 Theorem 25.1
6(b)	Lecture 18 Example 18.2	10(g)	Lecture 25 Theorem 25.5
		10(h)	Lecture 25 Example 25.3
		11(a)	Lecture 26 Theorem 26.6
		11(b)	Lecture 26 Example 26.4
		11(c)	Lecture 26 Example 26.5
		11(d)	Lecture 27 Theorem 27.1
		11(e)	Lecture 27 Theorem 27.1
		11(f)	Lecture 27 Theorem 27.1
		11(g)	Lecture 27 Theorem 27.2
		11(h)	Lecture 27 Theorem 27.5